

Citizen animals, dodo mayors – the curious account of a visit to Mauritius in 1632

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In 1887 a manuscript in the form of a letter to an unknown recipient, without any location given, was published under the headline of ‘famine in Surat in 1631’ (Servaas 1887). While the crisis in the Indian port city of Surat is itself of historical interest, the piece has had some attention in the dodo literature for its curious way of describing animals seen in Mauritius – each is assigned an anthropomorphised identity as if human inhabitants. Published in an obscure Dutch journal, most dodo writers have been unaware of the details. Of the few who noted it, Hachisuka (1953) had clearly only seen a partial second-hand account, whilst Wissen (1996) and Parish (2013), drew attention to the odd attributions and, as did Fuller (2002), bemoaned the lack of information on the source. Only the short passage on dodos themselves has appeared in print and in English translation since the 1887 publication. Pitot (1905), in his classic history of Dutch Mauritius, was unaware of this account and indeed wrote that after January 1629 “for another five years the Dutch did not land on our island, or at least no account mentions any such [landing]” (ASC’s translation).

The published account does not mention the ship the writer travelled on, but the dates match those of the *Ter Veere* given in *Dutch Asiatic shipping* (Bruijn 1979-87, Moree 1998; also <http://resources.huuygens.knaw.nl/das> & www.vocsite.nl/schepen). Colenbrander (1898) confirms the departure of this ship and others from Batavia [now Jakarta] to Surat, as described in the full Servaas text, but not mentioned in Bruijn’s compilation. The *Ter Veere*, a 350 ton East-Indiaman, captain Jan IJsbrandsz. de Jong, left Surat on 2 March 1632, joining the *s’Gravenhage*, which had left on 28 February, on the journey to Mauritius, arriving 29 April. They stayed at Mauritius until 19 May, proceeding to St. Augustine [Madagascar] where they remained from 17 July to 17 September before proceeding to the Cape (November to 2 December) and St. Helena where they waited till the rest of the original fleet joined them before sailing to Zeeland [Netherlands], which they reached on 1 May 1633. The *Ter Veere* had visited Mauritius before, also on a return voyage, 24 December 1628 to 16 January 1629, in company with the *Nassau* and the *Delfshaven*, all with sick crews (Pitot 1905, Moree 1998). They left after having revictualled with “tortoises, ‘perdrix’ [i.e. Red Hens], Dodos, pigs, palm-hearts, coconuts, dried fish and 70-80 goats embarked alive” (Pitot 1905,

ASC's translation).

Oddly to a modern reader, Surat is referred to in the text as being in 'Persia'; Colebrander (1898) likewise referred to 'Suratte en Persia' as the fleet's destination. The Mughal emperor Akbar, whose dynasty was of Persian origin, absorbed Gujarat, where Surat is located, into his empire in 1573 (Davies 1959). Surat was also one of the centres of settlement of the Parsis (= 'Persians'), Zoroastrian refugees who came to India in the eighth-tenth centuries CE (published dates vary) following the Arab, Turk and Mongol conquests of Persia (Boyce 1979).

While the human tragedy of famine is discussed in Surat (not translated), the account of Mauritius is confined to the anthropomorphised description of the animals they found there. Although the text only gives an explanation of these designations, and those given to the foodstuff on board, at the end of the letter, we have given the real name in square brackets at the first usage, to make the account easier to follow.

The principal biological importance of the passage is that it is the only eye-witness account to refer to what the Dodo ate – fruit. It is also one of only two accounts that mention the ability of dodos to use their bills to bite hard in self-defence, the other being the 'Verhuff' account of 1611, actually by Johann Verken (Parish 2013). It is also of some interest that the pigs are reported as thin and scrawny, suggesting they were short of food, and possibly explaining other reports of carnivorous behaviour (attacking and eating young goats and cattle; Cheke & Hume 2008: 81), in addition to the more normal feral pig diet of tortoise and turtle (and, no doubt, Dodo) eggs. The crew of the *Ter Veere* were evidently unaware of, and did not discover, the classic way of attracting Red Hens by waving a red cloth as described by so many other visitors (Cheke & Hume 2008).

The original has enormously long sentences which we have broken up into shorter stretches, but we have not altered the sense or sequence of the 17th century Dutch. Words added by us for clarity are in curly brackets {}; animal names are emphasized in bold for ease of reading. The translation is by HB and the commentary by ASC.

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Hongersnood in Suratta anno 1631 [Famine in Surat, 1631]

[the first section, pp.4-5 in the published version, concerns Surat; the Mauritius account starts on p.5]

So understand, beloved friend, that we left Persia on the 2nd March for the island of Mauritius, and have during the voyage been vexed¹ with the low nobility, to wit Sr Speckx [salt pork], miss Claren [fresh water], the Gentleman Ryswyck [boiled rice], Sir Jan Bruyn alias van Souten [salt meat], Sir Piscado Salada [salt fish], but the Gentleman Druyff [Spanish wine] left us, whom we hope to find again in our native country, and then to take up again our friendly conversation with him. But the Mr. Ryswyck, Miss Claren, and Sir Piscado Salada with Sir Speckx have mostly remained on a familiar basis with us, but Sir Jan Bruyn has been little in our company, as he has a horrible stinking breath, for which we cannot stand him, which misfortune will become worse and worse with him; as this is these days incurable, so he will be deserted by all. Passing the time in such a manner we reached the island on the 29th April, and came on land, to trade with the inhabitants, which were different in kind, to wit **mayors** [Dodos], **citizens** [pigs], **soldiers** [Red Hens], **tailors** [goats], **farmers** [tortoises] and **unknown inhabitants** [cattle], which we were unable to talk to, as they kept to the mountains.

Upon coming there we first found the **farmers**, which we greeted in their fashion, and they did not acknowledge at all, which we grew angry about, and took them prisoner on board, and tortured till death followed, and then skinned, cooked and then sent to their grave. As the others were surprised about this {they} went into the forest so that from then on we steadily robbed them, bringing aboard **mayors**, **citizens** etc. from which robbery we grew rich, and fattened our waists.

The **mayors** are very superb or well-mannered, they showed themselves to us with a stiff face and open mouth, very self-assured and cocky, hardly wished to move out of our way. Their war weapons were their mouths, with which they knew to bite sharply, their food was raw fruit. {They} were not very well-dressed, but were very rich and fat around the middle, so they were brought aboard in great numbers, to the contentment of us all. The **citizens** were very thin and scrawny of body, very grumpy, pushy and resentful, their gun was two curved long teeth, with which they defended themselves. They were dirty and messy, gave forth a horrible noise when we took them

1 We have translated ‘gevaccineert’ by vexed as this seems the sense, although *gevaccineert* cannot be identified in Dutch dictionaries old or new.

aboard as prisoners to do them to death like the others.

The **soldiers** were very small in stature and slow of foot, so they could be easily caught by hand, their armour or weapon² was their mouth, which was very sharp and pointed, and which they used instead of a dagger. {They} were very cowardly³ and skittish⁴, not striking like soldiers, {but} running about in great disorder, now here, now there, not being true to each other at all.

The **farmers** are very leaden⁵, plump and stupid, very scared of us and hating. They were very well armed and equipped, they have a hard thick shield on their back and their front, which serves instead of armour, their feet are covered closely with a tough skin, which serves instead of boots, when they go through water, also in the forest, through thistles and thorns, they cannot be damaged. {They} are very fertile and prolific, but lazy and slow, are not active in agriculture, indeed {they} gobble up more crop than they search to plant. As we therefore saw how useless they were for their country, we took many of them for our pleasure.

The **tailors** are their also in great abundance, but recalcitrant and cruel of face, rough of body, hard and thick of hands. {We} could not believe they could ply a needle, but are more inclined to war and robbery, as they are better armed than the soldiers, because they have two circular⁶ protuberances on their forehead, like twin horns, and this is their weapon of war, as they defend themselves with these. They produced a hoarse thin noise, when they saw us, with which they could warn each other, they always had a sentry on duty, and when that sentry started calling, young and old would flee into the forest, and they were very true to each other. They were not esteemed by the {other} inhabitants, because all the others from the principles of their birth bring their own clothing so that they have to live from robbery. I do not believe they would be esteemed in Batavia, because of the strange growth on their forehead, which would terrify the citizens of Batavia, as they could hardly believe they had ever seen such before. We took many of them prisoner and aboard.

On the **unknown inhabitants** we have been unable to write with any certainty, as we saw three or four from afar, very large it seemed, like giants compared to the others, and did not show themselves after.

I have set out below the names of the inhabitants, as well as the meaning how to translate, I cannot expand at present as these mentioned above are the principal {ones} of the island of Mauritius.

2 The original Dutch has 'geweer' (=gun) but 'weapon' seems a more appropriate translation; the same applies later to goats whose horns are said to be their 'oorloochsgeweer' (=oorlogs geweer, war gun).

3 The text has 'bloot' (=naked, bare), but we think the author intended *bloo[d]*, cowardly (see Sewell 1766).

4 'shou' in the original, presumably = *schouw*, of which the most likely meaning, in context, is skittish (Sewell 1766).

5 'lodtlich', presumably = *loden*, leaden, heavy.

6 'ronde' (round), but in reference to goats' horns must mean 'curved round in a circle'.

With this, dear friend, I command you to the protection of the most high who will give you and me what is blessed.

Explanation of names.

<i>Sr</i> [Sinjeur] Speckx [‘Sir Bacon’]	salt pork/bacon
(<i>j</i>) <i>uffrou</i> [miss] Claren [‘Miss Clear’]	fresh water
<i>dHeer</i> [Mr] Ryswyck [‘Mr Rice-refuge’]	boiled rice
<i>Sr</i> Jan Bruyn [‘Sir John Brown’] <i>alias</i> van Souten [or ‘Sir John Knocks-you-down’, alias ?? ⁷]	salted (meat?) [{word} torn off manuscript]}
<i>Sr</i> Piscado Salada [‘Sir Fish Salad’] [or ‘Sir Lettuce Bedwetter’ ⁸]	salted (fish?) [{word} torn off {manuscript}]
<i>dHeer</i> [Mr] Druyf [‘Mr Grape’]	Spanish wine

Explanation of the inhabitants of the island Mauritius

<i>Burgemeesters</i> [Mayors]	<i>dottaersen</i> [Dodos <i>Raphus cucullatus</i>]
<i>borgers</i> [citizens]	[feral] pigs [<i>Sus scrofa</i>]
<i>soldaten</i> [soldiers]	<i>velthoenders</i> [literally ‘field hens’, the standard Dutch name used for the flightless rail or Red Hen <i>Aphanapteryx bonasia</i>]
<i>snijders</i> [tailors]	[feral] goats [<i>Capra hircu</i>]
<i>boeren</i> [farmers]	[giant] tortoises [<i>Cylindraspis</i> spp.]
<i>onbekende inwoonders</i> [unknown inhabitants]	[feral] cattle [<i>Bos taurus</i>]

7 This name and the next appear to be puns – brown (*bruin*) is of course the colour of dried meat, and ‘y’ often substituted for ‘i’ in older Dutch, but also stood in for modern ‘ij’; *bruijen* was (Sewell 1766) to knock down, so, given the ‘bad breath’ (i.e. foul odour), noted for *Sr Bruyn*, it seems quite possible that the author was alluding to both colour and smell with his name – certainly in English a close whiff of really bad halitosis is said to knock the victim back or down. We have been unable to find a meaning for ‘van Souten’.

8 As with *Sr Bruyn*, this name appears to be a pun: *pescado salgada* (with a ‘g’) is ‘salt fish’ in Portuguese, but *pisgat* is (or was) a piss-a-bed [bed-wetter] in Dutch (Sewell 1766), though not in modern dictionaries; was the fish diuretic ?

A review on the current status of *Pelusios castanoides intergularis* BOUR 1983 on La Digue, Seychelles

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Abstract: The indigenous freshwater turtles *Pelusios castanoides intergularis* BOUR, 1983 was observed in its habitat on La Digue island, Seychelles from 2004 to 2014. Observations usually took place from late November to early December. Adult specimens were more or less regularly found at the river Mare Soupape and occasionally also at the Grand Anse river. Finding of adults turtles was strongly correlated with the presence of sufficient water bodies and thus during high water levels, individuals were found rather easily. In addition to adults, juveniles and hatchlings were also found associated with the Mare Soupape river, indicating that a viable population still exists on the western side of the island.

Introduction

The population of the freshwater turtles inhabiting the granite islands of Seychelles has faced a rapid decline during the past few decades (GERLACH 2000). Habitat destruction as well as population fragmentation and aging of populations were considered to be the major drivers of this decline (GERLACH 2008a). Conservation activities and population monitoring became important during the past 10 years (GERLACH 2002, 2008b, GERLACH & CANNING 2001, PAWLOWSKI 2010, 2013b, PAWLOWSKI & KRÄMER 2006, 2010). Furthermore, there is current debate on the endemic status of the existing freshwater turtles on the granite Seychelles islands. Whereas *Pelusios sechellensis* (SIEBENROCK, 1906) and *Pelusios subniger parietalis* BOUR, 1983 have been reported to be remnants of formerly introduced species, namely *Pelusios castaneus* (SCHWEIGGER, 1812) and *Pelusios subniger subniger* (BONNATERRE, 1789), the status of the last species *Pelusios castanoides intergularis* BOUR, 1983 remains unclear (FRITZ, et al. 2012, STUCKAS, et al. 2013). Despite this discussions, the area of pristine rivers and existing undisturbed marshland has clearly decreased significantly over the past decades, due to drainage and urbanisation. These wetland areas are not only habitat to the freshwater turtles, but also habitat and food resources for many other endemic animals in Seychelles such as the various dragonflies, the Seychelles swiftlet *Aerodramus elaphrus* (OBERHOLSER, 1906), Seychelles paradise flycatcher *Tersiphone corvina* NEWTON, 1867 or the Seychelles sheath-tailed bat *Coleura sechellensis* PETERS, 1868 (GERLACH 2007, 2011, HILL & CURRIE 2007, PAWLOWSKI & KRÄMER 2009). In fact, the focus on the conservation status of individual species may be extended to the habitat where many of the critically endangered species used to live in (PAWLOWSKI

& ROSE 2014). The river Mare Soupape on La Digue and its tributaries is amongst the most important ones on this island. The island still contains significant numbers of the freshwater turtle *Pelusios castanoides intergularis*. From 2004 to 2014 the population status of this freshwater turtle species was observed and the results are summarised in this work.

Material and Methods

From late November to early December regular excursions were carried out during the years from 2004 until 2014. The number of observation days ranged from 1 to 6 days per year. Main rivers and streams as well as ditches and ponds were visually checked for the appearance of freshwater turtles, namely *Pelusios castanoides intergularis*. Furthermore, turtles accidentally found on streets by tourists or island residents were brought to the headquarters of the Flycatcher Special Reserve throughout the year. Additionally, the water level of the water bodies within the habitats and weather conditions were assessed semi-quantitatively.

Observations in the habitat

The water levels in the habitat of the freshwater turtles varied during the various years, showing medium to high levels during the early years of observations, very low levels in 2012 and again medium to high levels from 2013 to 2014 (Fig. 1-4).

Fig. 1. Water levels at the Mare Soupape (upstream) during the various times of observations: a) 2008; b) 2010; c) 2012; d) 2014

Fig. 2. Water levels at the Mare Soupape (downstream) during the various times of observations: a) 2007; b) 2008; c) 2010; d) 2012

Fig. 3. Water levels at the Grand Anse (downstream) during the various times of observations: a) 2007; b) 2013; c) 2008; d) 2013

Fig. 4. Water levels at the Grand Anse (upstream) during the various times of observations: a) 2008; b) 2010; c) 2014

Table 1. Overview of observed *Pelusios castanoides intergularis* on La Digue between 2004 and 2014

Year	Days	West side (Mare Soupape)			East side (Grand Anse, Anse Petite)			Comments
		A	J	H	A	J	H	
2004	1	≥4	0	0	0	0	0	Sunny conditions; high water levels
2007	4	6	0	0	1	0	0	Sunny conditions; high water levels
2008	5	≥17	0	0	2	0	0	Medium water levels
2009	0*	0	0	>>1	n. o.	n. o.	n. o.	-
2010	6	3**	0	0	0	0	0	Medium water levels; partial algae bloom
2011	0*	1	0	0	n. o.	n. o.	n. o.	-
2012	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	Late rainy season, low water levels
2013	3	2	1	0	0	0	0	Early rainy season; high water levels
2014	3	5,2	0	2	2	0	0	Early rainy season, high water levels

n.o. - not observed; A - adults; J - juveniles; H - hatchlings;

*specimens found in the area were brought to the headquarters of the Flycatcher Special Reserve;

**one specimen found in captivity (captured in the same year)

The second freshwater turtle species inhabiting La Digue, namely *Pelusios subniger subniger* was not found during own observations in the habitat; however, during draining of one of the rivers (La Passe) for construction purposes, a few specimens captured temporarily (see also PAWLOWSKI & ROSE 2014). *Pelusios castanoides intergularis*, which was found at the same site were much higher in numbers (≥ 17 , Table 1). All other observations in the habitat refer to *Pelusios castanoides intergularis*.

Overall, the number of *Pelusios castanoides intergularis* found in the various potential habitats were rather low, never exceeding 10 individuals per observation period. However, during years with medium to low water levels (2010 to 2012), the number of turtles observed in the habitat was lower, and close to zero. One male crossing the streets of La Passe was found by tourists and was brought to the headquarters of the Flycatcher Special Reserve (Fig. 5).

During the years 2013 and 2014, in which water levels were rather high during the observation period, adult *Pelusios castanoides intergularis* could be found rather easily in both the Mare Soupape and Grand Anse rivers (Fig. 6, 7). A semiadult turtle was found in 2011 (Fig. 8). In addition to the observation of adults and subadult specimens, even hatchlings were found occasionally by passengers crossing open areas in 2009 and 2014. In addition to findings by third parties, both a single hatchling and a single juvenile was found by own observations in the area of the Mare Soupape in 2013 and 2014 (Fig. 9). Turtles were found active within the habitats either in the morning at about 8-10 am or in the late afternoon between 5 and 6 pm.

Fig. 5. Adult male *Pelusios castanoides intergularis* (Mare Soupape 2010).

Fig. 6. Two adult *Pelusios castanoides interularis* at Mare Soupape (upstream, 2014)

Fig. 7. A pair of adult *Pelusios castanoides interularis* from Mare Soupape (downstream; 2014)

Discussion and conclusion

Although the observation periods during the various years was limited to a few days per year and thus was considered as rather short, at least a few adult individuals of *Peluios castanoides intergularis* was found at the Mare Soupape or the Grand Anse river. Finding the turtles in the habitat was much easier once the rainy season when already started as the turtles had emerged from their dry season aestivation period (approx. May to September). This was especially evident in 2014, where the largest number of freshwater turtles could be observed at Mare Soupape, which had high levels of water in the main river section as well as in its tributaries entering the Flycatcher Special Reserve. At the Grand Anse river, restoration of the lower river section resulted in an improvement of the habitat by extending the water body and providing additional potential nesting sites and the very low end of the river. Thus, similar to Mare Soupape, it was quite easy to find individual turtles in this river. Turtle activity was similar to previous observations, showing peak activities in the morning and late afternoon hours (PAWLOWSKI 2010)

Hatchlings and juveniles, which have not been found at the Mare Soupape for many years and were detected only occasionally, indicate that the population at the western side is still reproducing. Previous investigations which failed to show any signs of reproduction at the La Digue population indicated that the population might be too small to be viable (GERLACH 2008a). However, this might not be the case for at least

Fig. 8. Semiadult *Peluios castanoides intergularis* from the Mare Soupape (2011)

the western side population due to the finding of hatchlings, juveniles and semiadults during the past years. Although the numbers of growing turtles found was rather low, the time span for observations were also short. Therefore, reproductive success might be even higher, especially during periods of extended rainfall, but may not occur in dryer years (PAWLOWSKI 2013a, WALSH 1984). As the observation period was very often limited to the onset of the rainy season, it is likely that more hatchlings may be found even later in the season. Based on the reproductive performance of many other aquatic turtles, it can be assumed that the deposition of clutches may appear about 4 to 6 weeks after completion of the aestivation/hibernation period, which is strongly correlated with the onset of the rainy season (ANDREAS & PAUL 1998, BECKER 2002, GRYCHTA 1999, LAMBERTZ & LAMBERTZ 2002, PAWLOWSKI 2015, 2016). The amount of food for both adult and juvenile turtles may be positively correlated with the amount of suitable freshwater habitats and therefore, again, an increase in rainfall pattern will contribute to the amount of suitable habitat for the turtles.

The number of observation days per year was rather low, and thus does not allow any extrapolation for both yearly and total population; however; based on a significant number of *Pelusios castanoides intergularis* being captured in 2009 during construction activities in only a small river section, it can be assumed that there are even more in the whole river. For instance, hatchlings and juveniles, which spend most of their early life time in camouflage, are extremely hard to find in the habitat. So, recent

Fig. 9. Juvenile *Pelusios castanoides intergularis* from the Mare Soupape (2013)

records of them could be due either to pure accidental finding or to an overall higher abundance. The finding of a juvenile and semiadult *Pelusios castanoides intergularis* furthermore indicated that not only does reproduction still take place on La Digue, but also that hatchlings can survive the first most critical years of life and may even reach maturity. This is considered as very good news for the indigenous population of *Pelusios castanoides intergularis* on this island as despite ongoing controversial systematic discussions, this freshwater turtle is still protected by national law.

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Observations on a nesting caecilian from Silhouette island, Seychelles

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Abstract: During several excursions into the ancient forest of Silhouette island in December 2015, several caecilians were found, which were believed to be all of the same species namely *Hypogeophis rostratus*. At the area of Gratte Fesse, a nesting adult female was found underneath a log, guarding about 4 eggs of about 1 cm diameter. Furthermore, several hatchlings were also found at the nesting site. These recent findings on the nesting female are in line with others several decades before, although the presence of hatchlings remaining at the nesting area has not been described before in scientific literature.

Introduction

The granitic Seychelles islands are currently inhabited by up to six endemic caecilians which are believed to be remnants from the old Gondwana continent (NUSSBAUM 1984). On Silhouette island, the fourth largest of the granite islands, all six caecilian species are considered as indigenous, although they may be hard to find and even harder to identify as a distinct species (GERLACH 2007; PAWLOWSKI & KRÄMER 2010). During several excursions along existing paths on Silhouette island from November 29th to December 11th, 2015, some observations on caecilians were made, including an observation on a nesting adult female.

Materials and methods

Excursions usually started between 8:00 and 9:00 h in the morning and lasted until about 16:00 to 17:00 h in the afternoon. The main route that was followed was the one leading from La Passe to Grand Barbe, and the routes from La Passe to Anse Mondon and from La Passe to Jardin Marron (lower part only) were observed once during this time. Small logs, bark and stones along this passage were carefully lifted and undersides were observed for any caecilians present. All pieces lifted were carefully turned back into its original position after observation in order to prevent any significant disturbance of the microhabitat.

Air temperatures were measured along the path at regular intervals (usually every 15 min) once or twice per walk using a digital thermometer (Amadigit, -40 to 120 °C; ± 1 °C).

Results

Weather and temperature conditions

The weather conditions ranged from slightly cloudy to raining. Measured temperatures ranged from 26.5 to 30.9 °C at the lowland forest area and from 24.8 to 28.6 °C at the mid and high latitude forest (Fig. 1).

Caecilians

All caecilians located in the forest area were solely found on the trail from La Passe to Grand Barbe in the mid- and high-altitude forest. The trail to Anse Mondon was found to be too dry and much too steep to be a suitable habitat for caecilians at the time of observations. The trail to Jardin Marron was too overgrown to take a more detailed analysis of the soil fauna.

Two adults and several larvae/juveniles were found which were deemed to be the same species (Table 1). The first juvenile was found underneath a piece of bark and measured about 8 cm in total length and was brownish in colour (Fig 2a-d). The second specimen was an adult of about 25 cm which was found underneath a stone at a flat river bed (Fig. 3a-d). Although, specific GPS data are missing, both locations were at the eastern side of the forest. The third location was at the western side of Silhouette on the way to Gratte Fesse. At this site an adult female of about 20 to 25 cm in size was found nesting underneath a larger log (Fig. 4a-d). In addition to this adult up to five eggs with a diameter of about 1 cm each as well as two to three hatchlings (about 8 cm in length). The eggs were all transparent and moving embryos with a dark upper and a light

Table 1. Date and number of caecilians found

Date	Location	Number of animals	Age status	remarks
05.12.15	1	1	Adult	Found underneath a flat stone
06.12.15	2	1	Hatchling 1 adult female	Found underneath a piece of bark
07.12.15	3	0,1,2-3	2 - 3 hatchlings 5 eggs	Nesting adult female, found underneath a log

Fig. 1. Temperatures measured at the trail from La Passe to Grand Barbe

Fig. 2. Juvenile *H. rostratus*. a) site; b) trail with bark pieces; c) juvenile; d) head area.

Fig. 3. Adult *H. rostratus*. a) site; b) rocks in the shallow river bed; c) adult; d) head.

Fig. 4. Nesting *H. rostratus*. a) site; b) wooden trunk with nest; c) nesting adult with eggs; d) nesting adult with eggs and hatchlings

underside could be clearly identified. Both adults and hatchlings were blackish in colour, however the underside of the hatchlings turned out to be lighter, similar to the embryos in the eggs.

Unlike the other caecilians found before, both adult female and hatchlings remained at this site and did not disappear even after a few minutes of observation before the log was placed back into its original position.

Discussion and conclusion

All specimens found were detected as individuals, with the exception of an adult breeding female which was associated with several hatchlings. The overall number of caecilians found along the trails on Silhouette was rather low, but comparable to other observations on La Digue or Mahé where caecilians were found only occasionally during the past years (pers. obs.). In all species (2 adults and one juvenile) found the tentacles are much closer to the nostrils than to the eyes. Based on the size of the adults, the species could be either *Grandisonia alternans* (STEJNEGER, 1893) or *Hypogeophis rostratus* (CUVIER, 1829) with maximum length of 156 to 330 mm and 204 to 365 mm, respectively (GERLACH 2007). The egg diameter of about 1 cm; however, corresponds to egg sizes known for *Hypogeophis rostratus* (up to 1 cm), whereas known egg diameter

for *Grandisonia alternans* ranged from about 4 to 5 mm (NUSSBAUM 1984). The presence of one of the adults in a shallow stream does not seem indicative for *H. rostratus*, but other caecilians (namely *Praslina cooperi* BOULENGER, 1909) have been found in small streams on Mahé (pers. obs.).

This was the first time a breeding female was found on the granite islands by the author during about 18 years of observations; however, breeding and guarding of the eggs is known from several Seychelles caecilian species (NUSSBAUM 1984). Although the nesting female was found during the rainy season (December), other authors reported that *H. rostratus* breeds throughout the year having clutch sizes of 6 to 30 ovoid eggs. Due to the high latitude of the rain forest, both rainfall and mist may not be limited to the typical rainy season, therefore soil moisture remains rather high all through the year. As the number of eggs including the hatchlings was at the lower end, it may be possible that some of the hatchlings have left the nesting site already, however, it remains unclear at this stage as the nest was only observed once.

Acknowledgements

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Some faunistic notes on selected moth species (Lepidoptera) from the Seychelles

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Abstract: In the present list two Lepidoptera species are mentioned for the first time for the Seychelles: *Autocharis marginata* and *Traminda obversata*. Several species are mentioned for the first time for the islands of La Digue (33), Mahé (1), Praslin (1), and Grande Soeur (1). The larval hostplant of the endemix species *Glyphodes duponti* is recorded as *Ficus lutea*.

Introduction

While the butterfly fauna of Seychelles is relatively well known (e.g. Lawrence 2000, Bolotov *et al.* 2015), there is still need for much more detailed studies on the moth fauna, though some publications contain much information already (e.g. Legrand 1965, Gerlach & Matyot 2006). Furthermore, there are some detailed studies on selected moth groups (e.g. Sphingidae by Matyot 2005) or on specific islands (e.g. Woods 2013), but some visits to the islands of La Digue and Mahé of the second author, and to Praslin of Maik Bippus, revealed several new moth species for those islands and even two species which had never been mentioned before from the Seychelles as a whole. The present faunistic notes aim at further advancing our knowledge of the moth fauna of this interesting archipelago.

The new records are from four islands all belonging to the granitic group:

La Digue (4°22'S 55°50'E), the fourth largest island of Seychelles, lying east of Praslin and west of Felicité, with an area of 10 km² and the highest point reaching 300 m;

Mahé (4°40'S 55°28'E), the largest island of Seychelles, with an area of 155 km² and the highest point reaching 905 m;

Praslin (4°19'S 55°44'E), the second largest island of Seychelles, lying 44 km northeast of Mahé, with an area of 37 km² and the highest point reaching 330 m.

Grande Soeur (4°17'S 55°52'E), the 12th in a descending series of Granitic islands, lying 6 km NE of La Digue and an area of only 84 ha.

The systematic order and nomenclature follows the one in De Prins & De Prins (2016). The general distribution of the species is taken from the same source, Afromoths, where references to the first published faunistic and biological records can be found. The specimens have not been caught, but only photographed.

Tortricidae

Eccopsis incultana (Walker, 1863)

La Digue, Calou Guesthouse, 03.x.2007, photo by P. Mazzei (Fig. 1). Formerly known from Curieuse, Mahé and Silhouette, **new record for La Digue**. Also distributed in Mauritius and São Tomé and Príncipe, and on the African continent in Gambia, Namibia, Nigeria, Sierra Leone, South Africa, Tanzania, Zambia, and Zimbabwe.

The larva has been found on the African continent on *Acacia tortilis* (Forssk.) Hayne, *Aeschynomene telekii* Schweinf. and *Piptadenia africana* Hook f., all Fabaceae.

Hyblaeidae

Hyblaea puera (Cramer, 1777)

La Digue, Calou Guesthouse, 03.x.2007, photo by P. Mazzei (Fig. 2). Formerly known from Aldabra, Cosmoledo (Menai), Mahé, Praslin, and Silhouette, **new for La Digue**. Also distributed in the British Indian Ocean Territory (Chagos), La Réunion, Madagascar, Maldives (Hulule), Mauritius (Mauritius and Rodrigues), and on the African continent in Botswana, the Democratic Republic of Congo, Gabon, Kenya, Mozambique, South Africa, Tanzania (Pemba island), Zambia, and Zimbabwe. It has furthermore been reported from the Neotropical region (Honduras, Mexico, Suriname) and the Oriental region (India, Indonesia, Myanmar, New Guinea and Sri Lanka).

The larva has been found on a variety of plant species belonging to Acanthaceae, Araliaceae, Bignoniaceae, Euphorbiaceae, Lamiaceae, Myrtaceae, Poaceae and Verbenaceae.

Pyralidae

Endotricha mesenterialis (Walker, 1859)

La Digue, Calou Guesthouse, 01.x.2007 (Fig. 3), 03.x.2007, 16.viii.2007 and 02.v.2014, all photos by P. Mazzei. Formerly known from Curieuse, Mahé, Sainte-Anne, and Silhouette, **new for La Digue**. Also distributed in the British Indian Ocean Territory (Chagos), and the Maldives (Hulule, Minikoi). The species has hitherto not been found on the African continent, but it is widely distributed with several subspecies in the Australasian region: Austral Island, Australia, Kermadec Island, New Caledonia, New Guinea, Palau Island, Samoa, Tahiti, and in the Oriental region: Begum Island, Christmas Island, India, Indonesia (Borneo), Malaysia (Sarawak), New Hebrides, Nicobar Islands, Sri Lanka, Tonga. The records from the Seychelles represent the most western distribution of this species, where it has been described as *Endotricha mesenterialis mahensis* Whalley, 1963.

The biology is unknown.

Hypsopygia mauritialis (Boisduval, 1833)

La Digue, Calou Guesthouse, 03.x.2007, 15.viii.2009 (Fig. 4), photos by P. Mazzei. Formerly known from Bird, Curieuse, Mahé, and Silhouette, **new for La Digue**. Also distributed in La Réunion, Madagascar and Mauritius. On the African continent it has been recorded from the Democratic Republic of Congo and Sudan, but these records need confirmation since earlier records from South Africa, Uganda, Zambia and

Figs 1–15. Moths of the Seychelles. 1. *Eccopsis incultana*; 2. *Hyblaea puera*; 3. *Endotricha mesenterialis*; 4. *Hypsopygia mauritialis*; 5. *Lamoria anella*; 6. *Autocharis marginata*; 7. *Cadarena pudoraria*; 8–9. *Cirrhochrsta muelleralis*; 10. *Cirrhochrsta perbrunnealis*; 11–12. *Cnaphalocrocis trapezalis*; 13. *Diaphania indica*; 14. *Diasemiopsis ramburialis*; 15. *Eurrhyparodes tricoloralis*. All pictures © Paolo Mazzei, except 14 © Maik Bippus.

Zimbabwe have proven to be erroneous (Leraut 2006). *H. mauritialis* has also been mentioned from the Australasian region (Australia, Hawaii) and from the Palaearctic region (China, Iran).

The larva has been found in nests of Hymenoptera, e.g. *Polistes* sp. (Martiré & Rochat 2008).

Lamoria anella (Denis & Schiffermüller, 1775)

La Digue, Calou Guesthouse, 21.viii.2009, photo by P. Mazzei (Fig. 5). Formerly known from Curieuse, Mahé and Silhouette, **new for La Digue**. On the African continent it has been recorded from South Africa and Sudan, and it is widespread in the Palaearctic region (China, South and Central Europe, Japan, Morocco, Oman, Palestine, Russia (incl. Far East), Syria, Tunisia, Ukraine, United Arab Emirates).

The larva has been found in nest of Hymenoptera, e.g. *Polistes* sp., *Vespa* sp., but it has also been found in silken tubes among low plants like *Aster* sp. and *Inula* sp. (Slamka 2006).

Crambidae

Autocharis marginata Guillermet, 1996 [**new for the Seychelles**]

La Digue, Calou Guesthouse, 01.x.2007, photo by P. Mazzei (Fig. 6). Until now only recorded from La Réunion, where it was thought to be endemic. Thus far only recorded in the Seychelles from La Digue. Perhaps *Autocharis linealis* Shaffer & Munroe, 2007, described from the Aldabra group, is a junior subjective synonym of this species.

The biology is unknown.

Cadarena pudoraria (Hübner, 1825)

La Digue, Calou Guesthouse, 13.viii.2009, photo by P. Mazzei (Fig. 7). Formerly known from Mahé, Praslin and Silhouette, **new for La Digue**. Also known from the Comoros, La Réunion and Madagascar, and from São Tomé and Príncipe. On the African continent very widespread and common in Angola, Cameroon, Democratic Republic of Congo, Equatorial Guinea, Ethiopia, Gabon, Gambia, Kenya, Malawi, Nigeria, Sierra Leone, South Africa, Tanzania, Uganda, Zambia, and Zimbabwe, but probably present in all Afrotropical countries. It has also been recorded from the Oriental region: India, Malaysia and Sri Lanka.

The larva has been found on *Gossypium* sp. and *Sida rhomboifolia*.

Cirrhochrista muelleralis Legrand, 1957

La Digue, Calou Guesthouse, 12 (Fig. 8) and 20.viii.2009 (Fig. 9), photos by P. Mazzei. Formerly known from Mahé, North, Praslin, and Silhouette, **new for La Digue**. An endemic species for the Seychelles, not encountered elsewhere.

The biology is unknown.

Cirrhochrista perbrunnealis Fletcher T. B., 1910

La Digue, Calou Guesthouse, 20.viii.2009, photo by P. Mazzei (Fig. 10). Formerly known from Curieuse, Mahé, Praslin, and Sainte-Anne, **new for La Digue**. An endemic

species for the Seychelles, not encountered elsewhere.
The biology is unknown.

Cnaphalocrocis trapezalis (Guenée, 1854)

La Digue, Calou Guesthouse, 03.x.2007 (Fig. 11) and 16.viii.2009 (Fig. 12), photos by P. Mazzei. Formerly known from Cerf, Fregate, Mahé, and Silhouette, **new for La Digue**. Also recorded from La Réunion, Madagascar, Mauritius, and Saint Helena. On the African continent it has been recorded from the Democratic Republic of Congo, Egypt, Gambia, Kenya, Nigeria, Senegal, Somalia, South Africa, Sudan, Tanzania, Uganda, Zambia, and Zimbabwe. It enters into the South Palaearctic region via Oman and Saudi Arabia and is also known from the Oriental region: S. China, India, Indonesia (Sulawesi), Papua New Guinea, and Sri Lanka), the Neotropical region: Dominican Republic, Mexico, and Peru, and the Australasian region: Australia, Fiji, Palau, Polynesia.

The larva can be a serious pest on various grasses, like *Oryza* sp., *Panicum trichodadum*, *Sorghum* sp., and *Zea mais*.

Diaphania indica (Saunders, 1851)

La Digue, Calou Guesthouse, 17.viii.2009, photo by P. Mazzei (Fig. 13). Formerly known from Aldabra, Aride, Bird, Coëtivy, Cousine, Fregate, Mahé, Praslin, Sainte-Anne, and Silhouette, **new for La Digue**. This species has been recorded in the British Indian Ocean Territory (Chagos), the Comoros (Mayotte), La Réunion, Madagascar, the Maldives (Hulule), Mauritius, and Saint Helena. On the African continent it is known from Cameroon, the Democratic Republic of Congo, Ethiopia, Gambia, Kenya, Malawi, Mozambique, Namibia, Rwanda, Sierra Leone, South Africa, Sudan, Tanzania, and Zimbabwe. It furthermore occurs in the subtropical and tropical zones of all the zoogeographic regions.

The larva feeds on several species of Amaranthaceae, Cucurbitaceae, Fabaceae, and Malvaceae. On the Seychelles it is reported from *Achyranthes aspera*.

Diasemiopsis ramburialis (Duponchel, 1834)

Praslin, 08.vii.2014, photo by M. Bippus (Fig. 14). Formerly known from Aldabra and Mahé, **new for Praslin**. This species is also recorded from La Réunion and Madagascar. On the African continent it is known from Cameroon, the Democratic Republic of Congo, Mozambique, Namibia, South Africa, and Zimbabwe. It has a cosmopolitan distribution and is mainly found in the subtropical and tropical zones.

The biology is unknown but the larva is supposed to live on Brassicaceae.

Eurrhparodes tricoloralis (Zeller, 1852)

La Digue, Calou Guesthouse, 12 and 14.viii.2009 (Fig. 15), photos by P. Mazzei. Formerly known from Aldabra, Denis, Mahé, Marie-Louise, Praslin, and Silhouette, **new for La Digue**. The species also occurs on the Comoros (Mayotte), La Réunion, Madagascar, the Maldives (Hulule, Minikoi), and Mauritius. On the African continent where it has been recorded from Cameroon, the Democratic Republic of Congo,

Gambia, Sierra Leone, South Africa, and Zimbabwe. It also occurs in the Australasian region: Australia, Fiji, Solomon Islands, and in the Oriental region: India, Indonesia (Java), New Guinea, Philippines, Sri Lanka, Taiwan, and Thailand. The biology is unknown.

Glyphodes duponti de Joannis, 1915

La Digue, La Mare Soupape, e.p. 25 and 26.viii.2009 (Figs 16, 17); La Digue, Calou Guesthouse, 02.v.2014 (Fig. 18), photos by P. Mazzei. Formerly known from Aride, Denis, Félicité, Long, Mahé, Marie-Anne, Round, and Silhouette, **new for La Digue**. An endemic species for the Seychelles, not encountered elsewhere.

As far as we know the biology of this species has never been described. The second author, however, found rolled leaves on *Ficus lutea* Vahl (Moraceae) at La Mare Soupape on the island of La Digue which contained brown pupae (Figs 19–21). Some adults emerged on 25 and 26 August 2009.

Palpita vitrealis (Rossi, 1794)

La Digue, Calou Guesthouse, 14.viii.2009, photo by P. Mazzei (Fig. 22). Formerly known from Aldabra, Mahé and Silhouette, **new for La Digue**. This species is also known from the Comoros (Mayotte, Mohéli), La Réunion, Madagascar, and Mauritius. On the African continent it has been recorded from the Democratic Republic of Congo, Ethiopia, Gambia, Lesotho, South Africa, Uganda, Zambia, and Zimbabwe. Via Yemen, it is furthermore distributed in the Palaearctic region (esp. South Europe), the southern parts of the Oriental region and it reaches Australia.

The larva lives on several *Jasminum* species and on *Olea europea* (Oleaceae).

Zebronia mahensis (Fletcher T. B., 1910)

La Digue, Nid d'Aigle trail, 18.viii.2009, photo by P. Mazzei (Fig. 23). Formerly known from Mahé, Praslin and Silhouette, **new for La Digue**. An endemic species in the Seychelles, not encountered elsewhere.

The caterpillar lives on *Tabebuia pallida* (Bignoniaceae).

Sphingidae

Cephonodes tamsi Griveaud, 1960

La Digue, Calou Guesthouse, 15.viii.2009 (Fig. 24); La Digue, L'Union, 15.viii.2009, photos by P. Mazzei. Formerly known from Mahé, Praslin and Silhouette, **new for La Digue**. This species is endemic in the Seychelles and currently known only from the four mentioned islands.

The larva has been observed on *Canthium bibracteatum* and on *C. carinatum* (Rubiaceae).

Temnora peckoveri (Butler, 1877)

La Digue, Calou Guesthouse, 13.viii.2009 (Fig. 25) and 26.iv.2014, photos by P. Mazzei. Formerly known from Denis, Mahé and Silhouette, **new for La Digue**. Also recorded from the Comoros (Grande Comore) and Madagascar.

Figs 16–30. Moths of the Seychelles. 16. *Glyphodes duponti*; 17. *Glyphodes duponti* (underside); 18. *Glyphodes duponti*; 19. Rolled leaf of *Ficus lutea* containing pupae of *Glyphodes duponti*; 20. *Ficus lutea*, foodplant of *Glyphodes duponti* with some rolled leaves; 21. *Glyphodes duponti*, pupa; 22. *Palpita vitrealis*; 23. *Zebronia mahensis*; 24. *Cephonodes tamsi*; 25. *Temnora peckoveri*; 26. *Phazaca theclata*, female; 27. *Phazaca theclata*, male; 28. *Thalassodes antithetica*; 29. *Traminda obsversata*; 30. *Achaea catella*. All © Paulo Mazzei.

The caterpillar lives on *Morinda citrifolia* (Rubiaceae).

Uraniidae

Phazaca theclata (Guenée, 1857)

La Digue, Calou Guesthouse, 01 (Fig. 26, female) and 03.x.2007 (Fig. 27, male), photos by P. Mazzei. Formerly also known from Curieuse, Félicité, Long, Mahé, and Silhouette, **new for La Digue**. The species is recorded from the other archipelagoes in the Indian Ocean: Comoros (Mayotte), La Réunion, Madagascar, and Mauritius and it also occurs on the African mainland: Democratic Republic of Congo (Katanga), Gambia, Guinea, Sierra Leone, South Africa (Gauteng) and on the Arabian Peninsula: Saudi Arabia and Yemen.

The caterpillar lives on *Paraserianthes falcataria* (Fabaceae) and *Stachytarpheta urticifolia* (Verbenaceae).

Geometridae

Thalassodes antithetica Herbulot, 1962

La Digue, Calou Guesthouse, 03.x.2007, 14.viii.2009 and 26.iv.2014 (Fig. 28), photos by P. Mazzei. Formerly known from Cousine, Mahé and Silhouette, **new for La Digue**. This species is endemic in the Seychelles and currently known only from the four mentioned islands.

The larval hostplant is unknown.

Traminda obversata (Walker, 1861) [**new for the Seychelles**]

La Digue, Daniella's Bungalows, 10.x.2007; La Digue, Calou Guesthouse, 12.viii.2009 (Fig. 29), photos by P. Mazzei. Thus far only recorded in the Seychelles from La Digue. The species is also known in the Indian Ocean from the Comoros (Grande Comore and Mayotte), La Réunion and Madagascar. On the African continent it occurs in Angola, Congo, Guinea, Kenya, Malawi, Nigeria, São Tomé, Sierra Leone, Zambia, and Zimbabwe.

The larval hostplant is unknown.

Erebidae

Achaea catella Guenée, 1852

La Digue, Calou Guesthouse, 02.v.2014, photo by P. Mazzei (Fig. 30). Formerly known from Aldabra, Aride, Cousine, Curieuse, Mahé, and Silhouette, **new for La Digue**. In the Indian Ocean the species also occurs on the Comoros, La Réunion, Madagascar, Mauritius and Rodrigues. On the African continent it is widely spread and known from Botswana, Democratic Republic of Congo (East Kasai, Katanga, Kinshasa), Eritrea, Ethiopia, Gambia, Ghana, Kenya, Lesotho, Malawi, Mauritania, Niger, Nigeria, Senegal, Somalia, South Africa, Sudan, Tanzania, Uganda, Zambia, and Zimbabwe. It also is recorded from the Arabian Peninsula: Oman, United Arab Emirates, Yemen (incl. Socotra) and from the Atlantic Ocean island of Saint Helena. It enters the Palaearctic region in Egypt.

The caterpillar has been recorded from several hostplants, e.g.: *Afzelia africana*,
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Bauhinia, *Lonchocarpus* and *Tamarindus* (Fabaceae), *Eucalyptus* (Myrtaceae), *Euphorbia pyrifolia*, *E. systyla* and *Ricinus* (Euphorbiaceae), and from *Terminalia catappa* (Combretaceae).

Achaea violaceofascia (Saalmüller, 1891)

Mahé, Sans Souci road, Copolia Lodge, 08.v.2014, photo by P. Mazzei (Fig. 31). Formerly recorded from Aldabra, Assomption, Cosmoledo, Praslin and Silhouette, **new for Mahé**. The species also occurs on La Réunion, Madagascar, Mauritius and the Mafia Archipelago (Tanzania).

The caterpillar is polyphagous.

Amyna axis Guenée, 1852

La Digue, Calou Guesthouse, 02 (Fig. 32) and 03.x.2007, Mahé, Daniella's Bungalows, 10.x.2007, photos by P. Mazzei. Formerly known from Aldabra, Aride, Bird, Coëtivy, Cosmoledo, Denis, Fregate, Mahé, Menai, Praslin, and Providence, **new for La Digue**. In the Indian Ocean it lives on the Comoros, La Réunion, Madagascar, Mauritius and Rodrigues. In the Atlantic Ocean it has been recorded from the Cape Verde Islands (Santiago, São Nicolao, São Vicente) and on the African continent from Cameroon, Democratic Republic of Congo (Province Orientale, South Kivu), Eritrea, Ethiopia, Gambia, Kenya, Mauritania, Nigeria, Sierra Leone, Somalia, South Africa (KwaZulu-Natal, North-West), Sudan, Tanzania, Uganda, Zambia, and Zimbabwe. This widespread species occurs also on the Arabia Peninsula: Oman, Saudi Arabia, United Arab Emirates and Yemen (incl. Socotra). It furthermore has a world wide distribution occurring in all zoogeographical zones, but it is unknown from Europe.

The caterpillar lives e.g. on *Beta vulgaris* and *Chenopodium album* (Chenopodiaceae).

Hyospila thermesina Guenée, 1862

La Digue, Calou Guesthouse, 26.iv.2014, photo by P. Mazzei (Fig. 33). Formerly known from Félicité, Mahé and Silhouette, **new for La Digue**. This species has furthermore been recorded from La Réunion.

The larval hostplant is unknown.

Mocis conveniens (Walker, 1858)

La Digue, Petite Anse, 04.x.2007; Calou Guesthouse, 06.x.2007 (Fig. 34), photos by P. Mazzei. Formerly known from Cousine, Félicité, Mahé, Poivre, Praslin, and Silhouette, **new for La Digue**. In the Indian Ocean the species also occurs on the Comoros (Mayotte), La Réunion, Madagascar, Mauritius, Rodrigues, and Zanzibar. In the Atlantic Ocean it has been recorded from the Cape Verde Islands (Santiago, Santo Antão). On the African mainland it occurs in Burundi, Cameroon, Democratic Republic of Congo (Bas Congo, East Kasai, Equateur, Katanga, Kinshasa, North Kivu, Province Orientale), Ethiopia, Kenya, Malawi, Nigeria, Sierra Leone, Somalia, South Africa, Sudan, Tanzania, Uganda, Zambia, and Zimbabwe. On the Arabian Peninsula it is only known from SW Yemen.

The larval hostplant is unknown.

Simplicia extinctalis (Zeller, 1852)

La Digue, Calou Guesthouse, 03.viii.2007 and 13.viii.2009 (Fig. 35), photos by P. Mazzei. Formerly known from Mahé and Silhouette, **new for La Digue**. In the Indian Ocean this species occurs on the Comoros (Mayotte), La Réunion, Madagascar, Mauritius, and Rodrigues. In the Atlantic Ocean it lives on the Cape Verde Islands (Santo Antão) and on Saint Helena. On the African continent it has been recorded from Ethiopia, Ghana, Kenya, Sierra Leone, Somalia, South Africa, Sudan, Tanzania, Zambia, and Zimbabwe. On the Arabian Peninsula it is known from Saudi Arabia and Yemen (incl. Socotra). The larval hostplant is unknown.

Utetheisa pulchelloides Hampson, 1907

Grande Soeur, e.l. 07.ix.2009 (Fig. 36) and subsequent days from caterpillars found early May 2009, photo by P. Mazzei; also some specimens reared from caterpillars found on 01.v.2014 on *Tournefortia argentea*. This species is widespread in the Seychelles archipelago: Aldabra, Aride Arros, Bird, Coëtivy, Desroches, Eagle, La Digue, Mahé, Poivre, Praslin, Rémire, Saint-Joseph, and Silhouette, **new for Grande Soeur**. Apart from the Seychelles, this species is known in the Indian Ocean from the British Indian Ocean Territory (Chagos), La Réunion (incl. Tromelin Island), Mauritius (incl. Cargados Carajos), and Rodrigues. It also occurs in the Australasian Region: a.o. Australia, Ellice Island, Gilbert Island, Marshall Island, New Zealand, Solomon Islands, and in the Oriental Region: Nicobar Islands, Singapore, Sri Lanka, and Taiwan. The caterpillar lives on *Tournefortia argentea* and *Trichodesma zeylanicum* (Boraginaceae).

Nolidae

Earias biplaga Walker, 1866

La Digue, Calou Guesthouse, 06 and 14.x.2007 (Fig. 37), 20.viii.2009, photos by P. Mazzei. Formerly known from Mahé and Praslin, **new for La Digue**. In the Indian Ocean this species also occurs on the Comoros (Grande Comore), La Réunion, Madagascar, Mauritius, and Zanzibar. In the Atlantic Ocean it has been recorded from the Cape Verde Islands (Brava, Fogo, Santiago, Santo Antão, São Nicolao, São Vicente). It is widespread and mostly common on the African continent: Burundi, Democratic Republic of Congo (Bas Congo, East Kasai, Equateur, Katanga, Maniema, North Kivu, Province Orientale, West Kasai), Eritrea, Ethiopia, Gambia, Ghana, Guinea, Kenya, Malawi, Mali, Mauritania, Mozambique, Nigeria, Rwanda, Senegal, Somalia, South Africa, Tanzania, Togo, Uganda, and Zimbabwe. On the Arabian Peninsula it has been recorded from Saudi Arabia and Yemen (incl. Socotra). It has also been mentioned from the Australasian Region: Samoa, Tonga.

The caterpillar lives on a wide range of mainly Fabaceae and Sterculiaceae. It has been found to damage *Gossypium* and *Theobroma cacao*.

Nola jourdani (Legrand, 1966)

La Digue, Calou Guesthouse, 03.x.2007, photo by P. Mazzei (Fig. 38). Formerly known from Mahé, Praslin and Silhouette, **new for La Digue**. This is an endemic species in the

Figs 31–45. Moths of the Seychelles. **31.** *Achaea violaceofascia*; **32.** *Amyna axis*; **33.** *Hyospila thermesina*; **34.** *Mocis conveniens*; **35.** *Simplicia extinctalis*; **36.** *Utetheisa pulchelloides*; **37.** *Earias biplaga*; **38.** *Nola jourdani*; **39.** *Callopietria maillardi*; **40.** *Chasmina candida*; **41.** *Chrysodeixis chalcites*; **42.** *Spodoptera cilium*; **43.** *Spodoptera mauritia*; **44.** *Stictopera antemarginata*; **45.** *Stictopera poecilosoma*. All pictures © Paulo Mazzei.

Seychelles, not occurring elsewhere.

The larval hostplant is unknown.

Noctuidae

Callopietria maillardi (Guenée, 1862)

La Digue, Calou Guesthouse, 10.x.2007, 26 (Fig. 39) and 27.iv.2014, photos by P. Mazzei. Formerly known from Coëtivy, Fregate, Mahé, North, Round, and Silhouette, **new for La Digue**. In the Indian Ocean this species also occurs in the British Indian Ocean Territory (Chagos), Comoros, La Réunion, and Mauritius. In the Atlantic Ocean it is known from the Cape Verde Islands (Fogo, Santo Antão), Equatorial Guinea (Bioko) and São Tomé. It is widespread on the African continent: Cameroon, Congo, Democratic Republic of Congo (Katanga, Province Orientale), Gabon, Gambia, Ghana, Kenya, Lesotho, Malawi, Nigeria, Rwanda, Sierra Leone, South Africa (KwaZulu-Natal, Mpumalanga), Tanzania, Uganda, Zambia, and Zimbabwe. It has not been recorded on the mainland of the Arabian Peninsula but it occurs on Socotra. It is widespread and mostly common in the Australasian and Oriental regions.

The caterpillar lives on *Asplenium nidus* (Aspleniaceae), *Nephrolepis biserrata* (Lomariopsidaceae) and *Pellaea viridis* (Pteridaceae).

Chasmina candida (Walker, 1865)

La Digue, Anse La Reunion, e.l. *Hibiscus tiliaceus* in October 2007 and September 2009, photo by P. Mazzei (Fig. 40). Formerly known from Mahé and Praslin, **new for La Digue**. In the Indian Ocean this species has been found in the British Indian Ocean Territory (Chagos), on Madagascar and in the Maldives (Hulule, Minikoi). It has been mentioned from South Africa and it occurs in the Australian (e.g. Fiji) and Oriental (e.g. Cambodia, S Japan, Singapore) regions.

The caterpillar lives on *Calophyllum inophyllum* (Clusiaceae), *Hibiscus tiliaceus* and *Thespecia populnea* (Malvaceae).

Chrysodeixis chalcites (Esper, 1798)

La Digue, Calou Guesthouse, 14.viii.2009, photo by P. Mazzei (Fig. 41). Formerly known from Aldabra, Arros, Bird, Coëtivy, Desroches, Eagle, Farquhar, Mahé, Marie-Anne, Poivre, Providence, Rémire, Sainte-Anne, Saint-Joseph, and Silhouette, **new for La Digue**. In the Indian Ocean this species occurs in the British Indian Ocean Territory (Chagos), the Comoros (Anjouan, Mohéli), La Réunion, Madagascar, Mauritius, and Rodrigues. In the Atlantic Ocean it has been recorded from the Cape Verde Islands (Fogo, Santiago, Santo Antão, São Nicolao), Saint Helena and São Tomé. It is widespread on the African continent: Angola, Botswana, Burkina Faso, Cameroon, Democratic Republic of Congo (Bas Congo, Katanga), Eritrea, Gabon, Gambia, Ghana, Ivory Coast, Kenya, Lesotho, Malawi, Mauritania, Mozambique, Niger, Nigeria, Somalia, South Africa (KwaZulu-Natal), Sudan, Tanzania, Uganda, Zambia, and Zimbabwe. On the Arabian Peninsula it occurs in Oman, Saudi Arabia and Yemen (incl. Socotra). It enters the Palearctic Region via NW Africa (Algeria, Morocco), Egypt, Libya, the Levant (Israel, Jordan, Lebanon, Palestine) and occurs throughout S Europe eastwards

through Syria, Turkey till China, Japan and Korea. It was introduced by man into Hawaii. Former records of the Australasian and Oriental regions refer to *Chrysodeixis eriosoma* (Doubleday, 1843).

In the Seychelles the caterpillar lives on *Achyrospermum seychellarum* (Lamiaceae), *Allamanda cathartica* (Apocynaceae), *Begonia seychellensis* (Begoniaceae), *Gloriosa superba* (Liliaceae), *Scaevola taccada* (Goodeniaceae) and *Tabebuia pallida* (Bignoniaceae).

Spodoptera cilium Guenée, 1852

La Digue, Calou Guesthouse, 02.x.2007, photo by P. Mazzei (Fig. 42). Formerly known from Mahé and Praslin, **new for La Digue**. In the Indian Ocean this species occurs on La Réunion, Madagascar, Mauritius, Rodrigues, and Zanzibar. It is widespread on the African continent: Democratic Republic of Congo (East Kasai), Eritrea, Ethiopia, Gambia, Kenya, Lesotho, Mauritania, Mozambique, Niger, Nigeria, Sierra Leone, Somalia, South Africa (Eastern Cape, Western Cape), Sudan, and Zimbabwe. In the Arabian Peninsula it has been recorded from Oman, Saudi Arabia, United Arab Emirates, and Yemen (incl. Socotra). In the Palearctic Region it occurs from NW Africa (Algeria, Morocco, Tunisia) through Libya, Egypt (incl. Sinai), Syria, Iraq, Iran, Turkey, Afghanistan till China, Japan, and Nepal. It furthermore occurs in the Oriental Region: India, Indonesia (Borneo, Java), Philippines and Sri Lanka.

The caterpillar feeds on grasses.

Spodoptera mauritia (Boisduval, 1833)

La Digue, Calou Guesthouse, 01 and 03.x.2007 (Fig. 43), photos by P. Mazzei. Formerly known from Cousine, Fregate, Mahé, Praslin, and Silhouette, **new for La Digue**. In the Indian Ocean this species has been recorded from the British Indian Ocean Territory (Chagos), the Comoros (Anjouan, Grande Comore, Mohéli), La Réunion, Madagascar, and Mauritius. In the Atlantic Ocean it occurs on Principe and on the African continent it lives in the Democratic Republic of Congo (East Kasai), Eritrea, Gambia, Kenya, Niger, Nigeria, Sierra Leone, Somalia, South Africa, Tanzania, and Zimbabwe. On the Arabian Peninsula it has been reported from Oman, Saudi Arabia, the United Arab Emirates, and Yemen (incl. Socotra). It furthermore occurs in the Australasian (e.g. Australia, Hawaii, Marquesas, Tahiti) and Oriental (e.g. India, Indonesia, Myanmar, Pakistan, Philippines, Sri Lanka, Thailand) regions.

The caterpillar feeds on grasses. In the Seychelles it has been reported to live on *Cyperus rotundus* (Cyperaceae) by Legrand (1965).

Stictoptera antemarginata Saalmüller, 1880

La Digue, Calou Guesthouse, 03.x.2007 (Fig. 44) and 13.viii.2009, photos by P. Mazzei. Formerly known from Félicité, Mahé and Silhouette, **new for La Digue**. In the Indian Ocean this species also occurs on La Réunion and Madagascar. On the African continent it has only been reported from the south-eastern region: Botswana, Mozambique, South Africa (Eastern Cape, KwaZulu-Natal), Tanzania, and Zimbabwe.

The biology is unknown.

Stictoptera poecilosoma Saalmüller, 1880

La Digue, Calou Guesthouse, 10.x.2007, 14 (Fig. 45) and 18.viii.2009, photos by P. Mazzei. Formerly known from Curieuse, Félicité, Mahé and Silhouette, **new for La Digue**. In the Indian Ocean it has been recorded from the Comoros (Grande Comore), La Réunion and Madagascar. There is one record of this species from the African continent (Tanzania) which needs confirmation.

The biology is unknown.

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Notes on Lepidoptera from the Seychelles

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Abstract: 53 species of Lepidoptera are reported from Mahé and Praslin, 44 species are illustrated. Genitalia images for 25 species are provided.

Key words: Lepidoptera, Seychelles

In July 2014 I spent a short holiday on the inner islands of the Seychelles (Mahé & Praslin) and took the opportunity to track some Lepidoptera. Apparently some islands, notably Praslin, had only scarcely been researched in the past. For Praslin 54 species of Lepidoptera are presently known although only very recently 11 species had been added by Bolotov *et al.* (2015). In this paper, I would like to share my results with the scientific community and I hope that this will incite other naturalists to undertake more research on the islands.

For Praslin I can add another 31 species of Heterocera, 3 new recorded species for the Granitic Islands of the Seychelles and I would like to point out to 3 possible new synonymes that will need additional verifications. I regret that I cannot myself examine the types of the different suggested synonyms for geographical reasons and I would like to invite other researchers to take a closer look at them at their next revision of the respective genera or families.

Stations: all Lepidoptera caught in Praslin were collected at Anse Boudin, at the junction of the main road to Zimbabwe at an altitude of 25m or the nearby surroundings (4°17'55''S, 55°42'35''E). The localities of the Lepidoptera collected in Mahé are indicated in the text.

Distribution records: for most species I only listed the distribution records available for the Seychelles islands, or, if otherwise interesting, the regional records (neighboring countries and Indian Ocean Island). For more precise distribution of the single species I would suggest to consulting the database of www.afromoths.com which has more recent information.

Space bars: 1 mm and 1mm divided in 100/100mm

Rhopalocera:

Borbo gemella (Mabille, 1884) – Pl.01, Fig. 01, 05

5 specimens collected on Praslin, Anse Boudin on 08.VII.2014. 1 male dissected slide SEY-043 (Fig.05).

Leptotes pirithous (Linnaeus, 1767) – Pl.01, Fig. 03

1 specimen collected on Praslin, Anse Boudin on 08.VII.2014. Wingspan: 24 mm.

Zizeeria knysna (Trimen 1862) – Pl.01, Fig. 02

2 specimen collected in Praslin, Anse Boudin on 08.VII.2014. Winglength: 8.5-9 mm

I also observed this species in Mahé (identification from pictures) on 01.VII. 2014 in Victoira, near the ferry jetty and on 02.VII. 2014, Anse aux Pins (cemetery).

Heterocera:

Sphingidae

Agrius convolvuli (Linnaeus, 1758) – Pl.01, Fig. 04

1 specimen from Praslin, Anse Boudin on 04.VII.2014

Wingspan: 96 mm

Hippotion gracilis (Butler, 1875) – Pl. 02, Fig. 06-07; Pl.03, Fig.11-12

2 male (one of them badly rubbed) from Praslin, Anse Boudin on 07/09.VII.2014.

Winglength: 32mm, Wingspan: 70 mm, Slide: SEY-082 (male) (Fig.11)

This species was treated as a synonyme of *Hippotion eson* (Cramer, 1779) until 2006 (Eitschberger, 2006) and records of *Hippotion eson* from the inner islands of the Seychelles might need reconfirmation.

Examination of the genitalia of specimen that I collected in Réunion (Fig. 06, 12) showed that these also belong to *Hippotion gracilis* (Butler, 1875).

Dr. Ian Kitching (BMNH) confirmed me that he doesn't know of any confirmed specimen of *Hippotion eson* from the Mascarenes (Réunion, Mauritius and Rodrigues) as well as Madagascar and that the records for *Hippotion eson* for the Malagasy region would also confirmation as well (pers.comm. 2015).

Biology: in Réunion I collected and raised its larvae from *Ocimum basilicum* L. (Lamiaceae) and *Morinda citrifolia* L. (Rubiaceae). Pupal stage: 25-30 days. Older host-plant records from Réunion (Martiré & Rochat, 2008) on *Alocasia sandieriana* (Schott) G.Don, *Zantedeschia aethiopica* (L.) Spreng., *Caladium bicolor* (Aiton) Vent., *Colocasia esculenta* (L.) Schott (Araceae), *Artemisia verlotiorum* Lamotte (Asteraceae), *Impatiens walleriana* Hook.f. (Balsaminaceae), *Geniostoma borbonicum* (Lam.) Spreng.(Logoniaceae), *Fuchsia* sp. (Onagraceae), *Danais fragrans* (Lam.) Pers., *Mussaenda arcuata* Poir. (Rubiaceae), *Cissus anulata* Desc. and *Vitis labrusca* L. (Vitaceae) most probably also refer to *Hippotion gracilis* and not to *Hippotion eson* as originally published. Earlier food-plant records for *Hippotion eson* from the inner islands of the Seychelles might also refer to *Hippotion gracilis*.

Epiblemidae

Phazaca theclata (Guenée, 1857) – Pl.02, Fig. 08-10

I found numerous specimens between 04.VII. and 09.VII.2014 on Praslin, Anse Boudin and 9./10.VII.2014 on Mahé, Ma Constance (Calypha Guesthouse), alt. (est.) 60-80 m.

Hostplant: in Réunion I bred this species on *Duranta erecta* L. (Verbenaceae).

Plate 01: Fig. 01 - *Borbo gemella* – Praslin; Fig. 02 - *Zizeeria knysna* – underside, Praslin; Fig. 03 - *Leptotes pirithous* – underside, Praslin; Fig. 04 - *Agrius convolvuli* – Praslin; Fig. 05 - *Borbo gemella* – male genitalia, slide SEY-042, Praslin. 05b: aedeagus

Plate 02: Fig. 06 - *Hippotion gracilis* – male, Praslin; Fig. 07 - *Hippotion gracilis* – larvae, Réunion. Top: early instar, bottom: late instar larvae; Fig. 08 - *Phazaca theclata*; Fig. 09 - *Phazaca theclata* – in situ, Praslin; Fig. 10 - *Phazaca theclata* – female genitalia, Mahé, slide SEY-022. 10b: sigma

Plate 03: Fig. 11 - *Hippotion gracilis* – male genitalia, slide SEY-082. 11b: detail aedeagus, 11c: aedeagus; Fig. 12 - *Hippotion gracilis* – female genitalia, slide RE-1128, Reunion. 12b: bursae, 12c: detail sigma

Plate 04: Fig. 13 - *Larentiinae sp.01* – Praslin; Fig. 14 - *Scopula minorata* – Praslin; Fig. 15 - *Pelagodes antithetica* – male, Praslin; Fig. 16 - *Pelagodes antithetica* – male, Praslin; Fig. 17 - *Pelagodes antithetica* – male genitalia, Praslin, slide SEY-048. 17b: aedeagus

Geometridae

***Larentiinae* sp.** – Pl.04, Fig. 13, Pl.05, Fig. 18

1 worn male collected on Praslin, Anse Boudin, on 05.VII.2014. Winglength: 7.5 mm
Most Larentiinae previously stated in or described from the Seychelles have hardly ever been illustrated – and naming the species that I found in Praslin would be pure speculation.

Gymnoscelis tenera Warren, 1901 is smaller in size (10-14 mm wingspan), *Chloroclystis gerberae* Herbulot, 1962 seems to have the same size but a different coloration (wing length 8 mm, Herbulot, 1962)

By its size it fits to descriptions of *Pasiphilodes subtrita* (Walker, 1866) with a winglength of 7-8 mm (Herbulot, 1962) but this species shows to have different genitalia (Fig.18) after the illustrations of Holloway (1997). The illustrated species from Praslin might well be an unrecorded species.

Pelagodes antithetica (Herbulot, 1962) – Pl.04, Fig. 15-17

Endemic to the Seychelles: Cousine, La Digue, Mahé, Praslin, Silhouette.

1 female & 6 males collected on Praslin, Anse Boudin, between 05.-09.VII.2014.

Winglength: female: 17 mm; male: 15-16.5 mm.

This species was recently redescribed (Bolotov et al., 2015).

Scopula serena Prout L.B., 1920

1 specimen on Mahé, 09.VII.2014, 2 specimens on Praslin, 06./07.VII.2014

Winglength: 6mm, Wingspan: 13 mm

Scopula minorata (Boisduval, 1833) – Pl.04, Fig. 14, Pl.05, Fig 19

2 female and 1 male on Praslin, 05-08.VII.2014.

Winglength: 9 mm, Wingspan: 19 mm

(slide SEY-061, female, 6.VII.2014; SEY-062, male, 6.VII.2014 – Fig.19)

Notable on this species from Seychelles is that the blackish cell spots on both wings are almost invisible. The male specimen has furthermore some irregular brownish markings on the right forewing.

Crambidae

***Autocharis* sp.** – Pl.06, Fig.20

The species observed on Praslin is without doubt near *Autocharis linealis* Shaffer J. C. & Munroe, 2007 described from Aldabra that is probably a synonyme of *Autocharis marginata* Guillermet, 1996 (Pl. 06, Fig. 21 & 24), described from Reunion island. Wingspan : 15 mm.

My only specimen from Praslin (Fig.20) on 06.VII.2014 escaped and I could not examine its genitalia. Though I still noticed that it's imago is identical to *Autocharis marginata* that I know well from Réunion.

From the images of imago and genitalia published in the original description of Shaffer & Munroe (2007) on *Autocharis linealis* I learnt that this species, described from Aldabra, is probably a synonym of *Autocharis marginata* Guillermet, 1996 (Fig. 21 & 24).

Plate 05: Fig. 18 - *Larentiinae* sp.01 – male genitalia, Praslin. 18b: aedeagus; Fig. 19 - *Scopula minorata* – male genitalia, Praslin, slide SEY-062. 19b: aedeagus 19c: 8th sternite

Plate 06: Fig. 20 - *Autocharis* sp. – near *A.linealis* and *A.marginata*. Praslin; Fig. 21 - *Autocharis marginata* – female, Reunion; Fig. 22 - *Cadarena pudoraria* – Praslin; Fig. 23 - *Cnaphalocrocis trebusialis* – Praslin; Fig. 24 - *Autocharis marginata* – female genitalia, Reunion, slide RE-1475. 24a : aphanosyses, 24b : bursae

Male & female genitalia are identical. The only small detail that I could not spot on the genitalia images published by Shaffer & Munroe (2007) are some projections on the apophyses (Fig. 24b). Though I believe that these might be present and had been covered by the outer skin of the abdomen on their picture. These projections on the apophyses are also not illustrated in the original publication by Guillermet. A future examination of types may give certainty on the (hitherto unconfirmed) synonymy.

Cadarena pudoraria (Hübner, 1825) – Pl.06, Fig.22

1 female on Praslin, Anse Boudin on 05.VII.2014. Wingspan: 32 mm

Cnaphalocrocis trebusialis (Walker, 1859) – Pl. 06, Fig. 23

1 specimen on Praslin, Anse Boudin on 04.VII.2014

Culladia inconspicuella (Snellen, 1872) – Pl.07, Fig. 25, 27

1 specimen on Mahé, Anse aux Pins, 03.VII.2014, two specimen in Mahé, Ma Constance (Calypha Guesthouse) on 10.VII.2014, 3 specimens in Praslin, Anse Boudin on 04.VII. (slide Sey-047, male), 05. and 07.VII.2014.

Former records of *Culladia admigratella* (Walker, 1963) from Seychelles are probably missidentifications and might refer to *C.inconspicuella* (Snellen, 1872), see Bleszynski (1970d).

Diasemiopsis ramburialis (Duponchel, 1834) – Pl.08, Fig.30

1 specimen on Praslin, Anse Boudin on 08.VII.2014

Diptychophora muscella Fryer, 1912 – Pl.07, Fig. 26, 28

Endemic to the Seychelles: Mahé & Silhouette.

1 male on Mahé, Ma Constance (Calypha Guesthouse), alt. (est.) 60-80m, 10.VII.2014.

Wingspan: 9.0 mm

Etiella zinckenella (Treitschke, 1832) – Pl.08, Fig. 29

One specimen on Praslin, Anse Boudin, 07.VII.2014.

Glyphodes duponti de Joannis, 1915 – Pl.08, Fig.31-33

Endemic to the Seychelles: Ande, Denis, Félicité, La Digue (pers.comm.Paolo Mazzei, 2014), Long, Mahé, Praslin, Sainte-Anne, Silhouette

1 male, collected 03.VII.2014 at daytime in Mahé, Anse aux Pins, 4°41'23''S/55°30'43''E, alt. estimated 265m (slide SEY-012), 2 female in Praslin, Anse Boudin on 06.VII.2014 (slide SEY-058). Wingspan: 3 4mm.

Glyphodes subamicalis Fletcher T. B., 1910 – Pl.09, Fig. 34-37

Endemic to the Seychelles: Mahé & Praslin

4 specimen on Praslin, Anse Boudin 2 female on 04./07.VII., 2 male on 04./05. VII.2014.

Plate 07: Fig. 25 - *Culladia inconspicuella* – male, Praslin; Fig. 26 - *Diptychophora muscella* – male, Mahé; Fig. 27 - *Culladia inconspicuella* – male genitalia, Praslin, slide SEY-047; Fig. 28 - *Diptychophora muscella* – male genitalia, Mahé, slide SEY-036.

Plate 08: Fig. 29 - *Etiella zinckenella* – Praslin; Fig. 30 - *Diasemiopsis ramburialis* – Praslin; Fig. 31 - *Glyphodes duponti* – female, Praslin; Fig. 32 - *Glyphodes duponti* – female, Praslin; Fig. 33 - *Glyphodes duponti* – female genitalia, Praslin, slide SEY-058.

Plate 09: Fig. 34 - *Glyphodes subamicalis* – male, Praslin; Fig. 35 - *Glyphodes subamicalis*; Fig. 36 - *Glyphodes subamicalis* – male genitalia, slide SEY-017, 36b: aedeagus, 36c: 8th sternite; Fig. 37 - *Glyphodes subamicalis* – female genitalia, slide SEY-052

Plate 10: Fig. 38 - *Haritalodes derogata*; Fig. 39 - *Hellula undalis*; Fig. 40 - *Herpetogramma licarsisalis*; Fig. 41 - *Herpetogramma* sp. nr. *basalis*; Fig. 42 - *Microcrambon paphiellus*; Fig. 43 - *Nacoleia charesalis*; Fig. 44 - *Poliobotys ablactalis*; Fig. 45 - *Pycnarmon diaphana*

Wingspan: female 33-35 mm, male 32-34 mm. (slide SEY-052-female, SEY-017-male)

Haritalodes derogata (Fabricius, 1775) – Pl.10, Fig.38

Seychelles: Mahé & Ile de Cerf.

1 specimen bred from larvae, collected in Mahé, Anse aux Pins on 02.VII.2014 in a residential area on *Hibiscus rosa-sinensis* L. (Malvaceae).

Hellula undalis (Fabricius, 1781) – Pl.10, Fig.39

One specimen on Praslin, Anse Boudin, on 05.VII.2014.

Herpetogramma licarsisalis (Walker, 1859) – Pl.10, Fig.40

2 specimens on Praslin, 06, 08-VII-2014, 2 specimens on Mahé on 10-VII-2014 (slide SEY-042, SEY-045)

Herpetogramma sp. nr. basalis (Walker, 1866) – Pl.10, Fig.41

2 specimens (one with badly damaged wings) on Praslin, Anse Boudin on 08.VII.2014.

Herpetogramma basalis is part of a species complex that had never been studied in modern times. (M.Shaffer in a pers.comm., published in Guillermet, 2009a) and its identity remains doubtful. I still would like to illustrate the specimen that I found in the Seychelles (Praslin).

Microcrambon paphiellus (Guenée, 1862) – Pl.10, Fig.42

Distribution: La Réunion, Mauritius, Seychelles: Mahé, Praslin, Silhouette

Several specimens of this species were observed on Praslin, Anse Boudin from 04.-07.VII.2014. Seems to be common in Praslin.

Nacoleia charesalis (Walker, 1859) – Pl.10, Fig.43

1 specimen on Praslin, Anse Boudin on 06.VII.2014. Winglength: 10 mm

Poliobotys ablactalis (Walker, 1859) – Pl.10, Fig.44

1 specimen on Praslin, Anse Boudin, 05.VII.2015. Wingspan: 21 mm.

Pyncarmon diaphana (Cramer, 1779) – Pl.10, Fig.45

1 specimen, collected 03.VII.2014 at daytime in Mahé, Anse aux Pins, 4°41'23"S/55°30'43"E, alt. estimated 250-280m. Wingspan: 25 mm.

Sameodes cancellalis (Zeller, 1852) – Pl.11, Fig.46

1 specimen on Praslin, Anse Boudin, 05.VI.2015. Wingspan: 18 mm.

Spilomelinae sp.01 (possibly *Phostria* sp., *Omiodes* sp. or allied genus) – Pl.12, Fig.51-52, Pl.13, Fig.56-57

Plate 11: Fig. 46 - *Sameodes cancellalis* – Praslin; Fig. 47 - *Zebronia phenice* – male, Mahé; Fig. 48 - *Endotricha mesenterialis* – male, Praslin; Fig. 49 - *Endotricha mesenterialis* – female, Mahé; Fig. 50 - *Zebronia phenice* – male genitalia, Mahé, slide SEY-090. Aedeagus: bottom left

5 specimens on Mahé, Anse-aux-Pins, approx. 25m altitude, mainroad (opposite of the Night Club), reared from *Canavalia cathartica* Thouars (Fabaceae) on 13.-15.VII.2014.
3 male, 2 female

Wingspan: 24-26 mm.

This seems to be an unrecorded species for the Seychelles. Due to its hostplant I believe that it might have an oriental origin.

Its female genitalia (Fig.57) shows some affinity to *Omiodes indicata*, with a long ductus bursae (length: about 3 times the bursae diameter) but in distinction with a shorter, round bursae with 2 signa (Fig.57b-c).

Only few species of Spilomelinae and *Omiodes* described from southern Asia or continental Africa had been illustrated. Genitalia images are not available for most species. This is also true for many other species included in similar genera such as *Phostria* (etc.) that have not yet been revised. Therefore I think it would be pure speculation to try to name this species for the moment.

Koen V. Maes from Belgium (pers.comm. 2016) suggested that this species has some resemblance with the African species *Phostria niphealis* (Walker, 1859) and *Phostria caniusalis* (Walker, 1859). Personally I think that this might also be the Indian species *Phostria obscurata* Moore, [1886]. A future revision of this family complex might help us out of this problem, and I hope that we can count on Koen for this. I would like to take the opportunity to thank Koen V. Maes also for his help, advice and suggestions on other questions concerning species of the Crambidae and Pyralidae families.

Zebronia phenice (Cramer, 1780) – Pl.11, Fig.47, 50

2 male collected 03.VII.2014 in Mahé, Anse aux Pins, 4°41'23"S/55°30'43"E, alt. estimated 250-280 m. Wingspan: 24 and 25 mm.

Pyralidae

Endotricha mesenterialis (Walker, 1859) (ssp: *E. mesenterialis mahensis*, Whalley, 1963) – Pl.11, Fig.48, 49

Seychelles: Curieuse, Mahé, Praslin, Silhouette, St.Anne

Numberous specimens were collected on Praslin and Mahé between 03.VII. and 10.VII.2014. This is one of the most abundant species that I found in the Seychelles.

Wingspan: 18 mm

Cosmopterigidae

Gisilia armigera (Meyrick, 1923) – Pl.14, Fig.58-62

1 female on Praslin, Anse Boudin, 07-VII-2014 (Fig.61 - slide SEY-088). Wingspan: 8 mm

Gisilia armigera, described from Fiji, is also present in Réunion and Mauritius (new records).

The female genitalia (Fig.61, slide SEY-088) of the only specimen collected on Praslin corresponds to the specimen of this species that I also find in Réunion. Though I think that it would be good to obtain additional specimen from the Seychelles and confirm its identity by a male (Fig.62) that is far more recognizable by its asymmetrical valvae and the S-shaped aedeagus.

Plate 12: Fig. 51 - *Spilomelinae* sp.01; Fig. 52 - *Spilomelinae* sp.01; Fig. 53 - *Dichomeris acuminata*; Fig. 54 - *Thiotricha tenuis*; Fig. 55 - *Thiotricha tenuis* – male genitalia 55b: aedeagus

Plate 13: Fig. 56 - *Spilomelinae* sp.01 – male genitalia. 56b: aedeagus; Fig. 57 - *Spilomelinae* sp.01 – female genitalia 57b: bursae 57c: detail sigma

Plate 14: Fig. 58 - *Gisilia armigera*; Fig. 59 - *Gisilia armigera* – wing venation ; Fig. 60 - *Gisilia armigera* – in situ, Praslin; Fig. 61 - *Gisilia armigera* – female genitalia, Praslin 61b: detail sigma; Fig. 62 - *Gisilia armigera* – male genitalia, Réunion. Aedeagus below

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Plate 15: Fig. 63 - *Achaea violaceofasciata* ssp. *seychellarum*; Fig. 64 - *Hyospila bolinoides*; Fig. 65 - *Hyospila bolinoides*; Fig. 66 - *Amyna axis*; Fig. 67 - *Hyospila bolinoides* – female genitalia.

This species might have its origins in Australia. Known hostplants of species of the *Gisilia/Ascalenia/Bifascioides* complex from the Palaearctic ecozone and India are *Acacia* ssp. (Kasy, 1968, 1970a; Fletcher, 1933). Most *Acacia* species found on the islands of the Indian Ocean (and also in Fiji) were introduced from Australia.

Unfortunately the Australian species of this complex have not been revised and no genitalia had been published in modern times. Therefore it is presently impossible to determine if this species might be a synonym of another Australian species, or not.

There is another species of the *Ascalenia/Bifascioides/Gisilia* complex that had been described from the Seychelles (Mahé) and that has a similar coloration (Gerlach & Matyot, 2006: pl. 6, Fig.2): *Ascalenia isotacta* (Meyrick, 1911). Thanks to Dr. Lees of the British Museum of Natural History I obtained a photograph of its type and it seems to have a different blackish punctuation on the forewings. In addition it looks to be scattered with more greyish scales.

Mrs. Jurate de Prins (formerly BMNH) informed me already in early 2015 that the type series had not been dissected.

Erebidae

Achaea violaceofasciata Saalmüller, 1891; *ssp. seychellarum* Holland, 1895 – Pl.15, Fig. 63

2 specimens on Praslin on 05. and 06.VII.2014 (one male dissected).

I would like to thank Mr. Albert Legrain (Belgium) for his great help and for sending me the pictures of the MNHN collection from Aldabra & Madagascar of this subspecies.

Amyna axis Guenée, 1852 – Pl.15, Fig.66

One specimen with damaged wings (Fig.66) on Praslin, Anse Boudin on 04.VII.2014.

Gesonia obeditalis Walker, 1859

1 specimen on Praslin, Anse Boudin, on 08.Jul.2014.

Hyospila bolinoides (Guenée, 1852) – Plate 15, Fig.64, 65, 67

Synonyms (Holloway, 2005): *Hyospila thermesina* Guenée, 1862, *Hyospila andamana* Swinhoe, 1919, *Moepa concisa* Walker, 1865, *Thermesia orientalis* Leech, 1900, *Thermesia signipalpis* Walker, 1858

Distribution: Andaman and Nicobar Islands, China, India, Indonesia (Java) Japan, New Guinea, Queensland and the Carolines.

Seychelles: Felicité, La Digue, Mahé, Silhouette & Praslin

Doubtful: La Réunion

1 female from Praslin, Anse Boudin on 06.VII.2014. Wingspan: 31 mm

In La Réunion and the Seychelles there is some confusion about this species. Most literature cites this species as *Hyospila thermesina* Guenée, 1862 although this was first treated as a synonym of *Hyospila bolinoides* by de Joannis (1899) furthermore by Fryer (1912) and Holloway (2005). Both, de Joannis (1899) and Fryer (1912) treated *Hyospila bolinoides* as a synonym of *Hyospila thermesina*. They probably ignored the publication dates for these species and inverted the names. Guénée had purchased

the type from a merchant and possibly the origin of the type specimen of *Hyospila thermesina* was incorrectly transmitted to Guenée as being from La Réunion.

Hyospila bolinoides is a variable species and even Guenée (1862) mentioned in the original description of *H. thermesina* that it differs only in the length of the 3rd articulation of the palpa from *H. bolinoides* and that the same is more dressed.

Citation from the original description of Guenée (1862) :

« J'ai acheté cet insecte d'un marchand qui l'a reçu de l'île de la Réunion. Il partage et confirme tous les caractères de mon genre *Hyospila*: seulement le troisième article des palpes est plus long et plus redressé que chez la *Bolinoides*. ».

Unfortunately the abdomen of my only specimen from Praslin was completely infested by a parasite. Corpus and ductus bursae were complete destroyed. Though, it shows some small differences in the ostium of the female genitalia (Fig.67) compared to the illustrations of Holloway (1997) in *Moths of Borneo*. Alberto Zilli (BMNH) noticed on my specimen also a difference on the crenulated postmedial line on the hindwing (A.Zilli, pers.comm.) and suggested that a different species might be involved. It will certainly be helpful to obtain more specimen to clear the exact position of this species from the Seychelles.

In Réunion this species had never been caught since its description (pers.comm. C.Guillermet, J.Rochat and my own captures). Due to the uncertain source of acquisition of the type, I consider its presence in Réunion as doubtful.

Hostplant: unknown.

Holloway (2005) indicates *Derris* sp. (Fabaceae) for *H. bolinoides* in Asia. There is found one native species of this genus in the Seychelles: *Derris trifoliata* Lour. that might be a possible hostplant that would need verification. This species of plant is also found in tropical Asia and Austral-Pacific region (USDA, ARS, National Genetic Resources Program, acc.2015).

Ozarba perplexa Saalmüller, 1891 – Pl.16, Fig.68-71, Pl.17, Fig.74

Distribution: Kenya, La Réunion, Madagascar, Socotra, South Africa, Zambia, Seychelles: Praslin & Mahé

2 male from Praslin, Anse Boudin, on 06.VII.2014 (slide SEY-015). Winglength: 9-10 mm, Wingspan: 22-23 mm.

Ozarba perplexa, described from Madagascar, was reported from the Seychelles by Legrand (1965). Berio (1954) illustrated the male genitalia.

This species is identical with *Microplexia costimaculalis* Guillermet, 1992, described from La Réunion, in imago and genitalia though I regret that I could not yet examine their types.

Hostplant: The main hostplant of this species is *Asystasia gangetica* (L.T.Anderson) (Acanthaceae). Sevastopulo (1978) had already reported this species on *Asystasia* sp. from East Africa. Martiré & Rochat (2008) report it also on *Clerodendrum speciosissimum* Drapiez (Verbenaceae).

It was treated as rare in La Réunion though I find it regularly throughout the year, both, larvae and adults. On my own and on the neighboring ground there is a rather big field of *A.gangetica* which may explain why I find it more frequently than other collectors

Plate 16: Fig. 68 - *Ozarba perplexa*; Fig. 69 - *Ozarba perplexa*; Fig. 70 - *Ozarba perplexa* – male genitalia 70b: aedeagus; Fig. 71 - *Ozarba perplexa* – female genitalia.

Plate 17: Fig. 72 - *Simplicia extinctalis*; Fig. 73 - *Rivula dimorpha*; Fig. 74 - *Ozarba perplexa* – caterpillar; Fig. 75 - *Rivula dimorpha* – caterpillar; Fig. 76 - *Rivula dimorpha* – male genitalia 76b: aedeagus

Plate 18: Fig. 77 - *Stictoptera antemarginata*, morphe *pernigra* – male, Praslin; Fig. 78 - *Stictoptera antemarginata* – female, Praslin; Fig. 79 - *Stictoptera antemarginata* – female genitalia, slide SEY-013 79b: bursae 79c: sigma; Fig. 80 - *Stictoptera antemarginata* – male genitalia, slide SEY-051 80b: aedeagus

Plate 19: Fig. 81 - *Pardasena mangifera* – male, Mahé; Fig. 82 - *Pardasena mangifera* – male, Mahé; Fig. 83 - *Pardasena mangifera* – female genitalia, Praslin; Fig. 84 - *Pardasena mangifera* – male genitalia 84b: aedeagus 84c: 8th sternite

in the past. *A.gangetica* is also present on the roadsides in Anse Boudin, Praslin where I collected the specimen. This plant is considered as a possibly native plant in the Seychelles. In Réunion it is treated as introduced and invasive.

O. perplexa is also present in Mauritius (new record). In June 2016 I also collected an adult in Flic-en-Flac and mature larvae, also on *Asystasia gangetica*, in Rivière Noire.

Rivula dimorpha Fryer, 1912 – Pl.17, Fig. 73, 75, 76

Distribution: La Réunion and Seychelles: Mahé, Praslin & Silhouette

1 male in Praslin, Anse Boudin on 05.VII.2014 (slide SEY-040).

Hostplant: in La Réunion I bred this species from *Cynodon dactylon* (L.) Pers. (Poaceae) and from another unidentified Poaceae sp.

Simplicia extinctalis (Zeller, 1852) – Pl.17, Fig.72

1 female in Mahé, on 10.VII.2014 and a damaged male (Fig.71) on 07.VII.2014 in Praslin, Anse Boudin. Wingspan: 27 mm

Hostplant: The caterpillars of this species were found and raised on mango leaf litter (*Mangifera indica* L.) in January 2015 by Guillaume Julliard (pers.comm.) in La Réunion.

Noctuidae

Chrysodeixis chalcites (Esper, 1789)

Seychelles: Aldabra, Arros, Bird, Remire ('Eagle'), Coëtivy, Desroches, Mahé, Poivre, Praslin, Providence, St.Anne & Silhouette

1 male from Praslin, Anse Boudin on 06.VII.2014.

Hostplant: *C.chalcites* is an extremely polyphagous species. In Réunion I bred it from *Ocimum basilicum* L. (Lamiaceae), *Ageratum conyzoides* L., *Synedrella nodiflora* (L.) Gaertn. (Asteraceae), *Kalanchoe* sp. (Crassulaceae), *Duranta erecta* L., *Stachytarpheta jamaicensis* (L.) Vahl (Verbenaceae), *Solanum lycopersicum* L., *Solanum mauritianum* Scop. (Solanaceae), *Trema orientalis* (L.) Blume (Cannabaceae) and *Melochia pyramidata* L. (Malvaceae).

Stictoptera antemarginata Saalmüller, 1880 – Pl.18, Fig. 77-80

1 male, morphe pernigra (genitalia slide SEY-051, Fig.77, 80) and 2 fairly worn females (genitalia slide SEY-013, Fig.78, 79) on Praslin, Anse Boudin, on 07. and 09.VII.2014.

Wingspan: 35 mm.

The bursae of the female shows a very small signa (Fig.79c)

Nolidae

Nycteola mauritia (de Joannis, 1906)

Distribution: La Réunion, Mauritius, Seychelles: Mahé & Praslin

1 female on Praslin, Anse Boudin, on 08.VII.2014.

Hostplant: in Réunion I bred this species from *Syzygium cumini* (L.) Skeels, *Syzygium jambos* (L.) Alston and *Syzygium cymosum* (Lam.) DC. (Myrtaceae).

Pardasena mangifera (Tams, 1938) n.comb. – Pl.19, Fig. 81-84

Original combination: *Symitha mangifera* Tams, 1938

Seychelles: Mahé and Praslin

1 male from Mahé, 10.VII.2014 (slide SEY-038), 1 female from Praslin, 08.VII.2014 (slide SEY-053). Wingspan: 18 mm.

This species was described by 4 females and had not been retrieved since its description in 1938.

By the male genitalia (Fig.84) this species belongs to the genus *Pardasena* (n.comb). The female has a elongated signa at the bursae (Fig.83).

Hostplant: the type series (4 females) was bred on young mango leaves (*Mangifera indica* L.) by D.V. Fitzgerald in 1938 (Tams, 1938).

Note: Legrand (1966) did not mention this species in his remarkable publication on Seychelles lepidoptera – possibly this species was unknown to him when describing *Pardasena beauvallonensis* Legrand, 1966. He did not publish genitalia images and from his plate the details of the wings are not recognizable. I think it should be interesting to compare both species in a future revision of the genus.

Gelechiidae

Dichomeris acuminata (Staudinger, 1876) – Pl.12, Fig. 53

Two specimen in Praslin, Anse Boudin on 05./08.VII.2014.

Thiotricha tenuis (Walsingham, 1891) – Pl.12, Fig. 54, 55

Seychelles: Aldabra, Cerf, Cosmoledo, Mahé, Praslin, Silhouette

One male on Praslin, Anse Boudin on 08.VII.2014. Winglength: 3.8 mm, wingspan: 8.5mm.

Gelechiidae sp.01 – Pl.23, Fig.98-101

One specimen on Praslin, Anse Boudin, on 06.VII.2014 (Fig.98). Wingspan: 9 mm.

I could not name this small species but I believe it might have a large distribution. I also find it in Réunion where I bred it from *Tamarindus indica* L. (Fabaceae) and *Trema orientalis* (L.) Blume (Cannabaceae). This seems to be an unrecorded species from both countries: Seychelles and Réunion. Its hostplants are widely distributed in the African/Asian countries and this Gelechiidae sp. has certainly a broad distribution.

Brachmia fuscogramma Janse, 1960 – Pl.22, Fig. 95-97

Distribution: Réunion, South Africa, Zimbabwe

This species was described from specimen from South Africa and Zimbabwe and I did not encounter it during my visit to the Seychelles. Though, I would still like to take the opportunity to illustrate it in this paper as I noticed that its imago is identical to *Brachmia brunneolineata* Legrand, 1966 described from the Seychelles.

Unfortunately Legrand did not publish a genitalia illustration of his species and it will be necessary to examine the types to find out if it might be a junior synonym of *Brachmia fuscogramma*.

Plate 20: Fig. 85 - *Stathmopoda auriferella*; Fig. 86 - *Stathmopoda morellela*; Fig. 87 - *Stathmopoda auriferella* – female genitalia, slide SEY-049; Fig. 88 - *Stathmopoda morellela* – female genitalia

Plate 21: Fig. 89 - *Erechthias sp. nr. molynta*; Fig. 90 - *Erechthias sp. nr. molynta*; Fig. 91 - *Erechthias sp. nr. molynta* – male genitalia 91b: aedeagus; Fig. 92 - *Erechthias sp. nr. molynta* – female genitalia 92b: ostium

Plate 22: Fig. 93 - *Cryptophlebia peltastica*; Fig. 94 - *Thaumatovalva limbata*; Fig. 95 - *Brachmia fuscogramma* – Réunion; Fig. 96 - *Brachmia fuscogramma* – Réunion; Fig. 97 - *Brachmia fuscogramma* – male genitalia. 97b: aedeagus

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99

100

100b

101b

101

Plate 23: Fig. 98 - *Gelechiidae sp.01*; Fig. 99 - *Gelechiidae sp.01*; Fig.100- *Gelechiidae sp.01* – female genitalia. 100b: bursae; Fig. 101- *Gelechiidae sp.01* – male genitalia. 101b: aedeagus

The illustrated specimen (Fig.95-97) provides from La Réunion, La Possession, alt.400m where it seems to be rare. The only specimen (male, slide RE-1872, wingspan:10.5 mm) was captured on 11.VI.2015.

Stathmopodidae

Stathmopoda auriferella (Walker, 1864) – Pl.20, Fig.85, 87

Seychelles : Mahé, Praslin, Silhouette

Several specimens were observed on Praslin on 04-05.VII. and 08.VII.2014. Wingspan 10.5 mm. This seems to be a common species.

Stathmopoda morellela Legrand, 1966 – Pl.20, Fig.86, 88

Endemic to the Seychelles: Mahé, Praslin & Silhouette

1 female from Praslin, Anse Boudin on 04.VII.2014. Wingspan: 19 mm.

Tineidae

Erechthias sp. nr. molynta (Meyrick, 1911) – Pl.21, Fig.89-92

3 specimens on Mahé, Ma Constance, 09-10.VII.2014. Wingspan: 17 mm.

From the male genitalia (Fig.91) the illustrated species seems to be an *Erechthias* but I could not attribute it surely to a species. From the original description and the drawing published by Gerlach & Matyot (2006) it might correspond to *Erechthias molynta* in size and coloration.

Note : the darker field on the female bursae (Fig.92) is an air bubble in the slide.

Tortricidae

Cryptophlebia peltastica (Meyrick, 1921)

1 specimen collected on Praslin, Anse Boudin on 05.VII.2014

Hostplant: In Réunion I bred this species from fruits of *Pithecellobium dulce* (Roxb.) and *Bauhinia monandra* Kurz (Fabaceae).

Dudua aprobola (Meyrick, 1886) – Pl.22, Fig.93

Seychelles: Aride, Curieuse, Mahé, Praslin, Silhouette

1 male, 1 female on Praslin, Anse Boudin on 08.VII.2014.

Hostplant: In Réunion I bred this species from *Syzygium jambos* (L.) Alston (Myrtaceae), *Mangifera indica* L. (Anacardiaceae) and *Trema orientalis* (L.) Blume (Cannabaceae).

Thaumatovalva limbata (Diakonoff, 1969) – Pl.22, Fig.94

Distribution: Kenya & Seychelles: Aldabra, Cosmoledo, Mahé, Praslin

1 specimen collected on Praslin, Anse Boudin on 07.VII.2014

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Sticks and stones: notes on the ecology and conservation of an endemic stick insect (*Apterograeffea marshallae*) and the restoration of an island ecosystem

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Abstract: The Mascarene Islands (Mauritius, Rodrigues, and Réunion) of the western Indian Ocean are home to a diversity of endemic flora and fauna, often linked through close evolutionary and ecological relationships. Owing to a turbulent history of anthropogenic exploitation, contemporary research and habitat restoration efforts are underway on Mauritius and numerous surrounding islets, notably Round Island. The Round Island stick insect, *Apterograeffea marshallae* (Phasmatodea: Platycraninae), was described in 2002 and information about the species' biology has been wanting. In this short communication we confirm the importance of the endangered Blue Latan Palm (*Latania loddigesii*) in the diet of the Round Island stick insect and include observations on reproduction and predation of this insect species. These observations are relevant for informing ongoing habitat restoration and conservation efforts in the Mascarenes, as well as the biology of the stick insect *A. reunionensis* on Réunion. Despite their roles as prey, predators, and pollinators, insects are disproportionately overlooked as conservation priorities. We suggest that conservation projects would greatly benefit from directed study of oft-neglected insects to supplement knowledge of species biology, reconstruct ecological histories, re-establish lost ecological interactions, and restore integrity of ecological communities.

Keywords: conservation; ecological restoration; island biogeography; Mauritius; natural history; Phasmatodea (Phasmida); plant-animal interactions.

Introduction

In the western Indian Ocean, laying approximately 900 km east of Madagascar, the Mascarene Islands (Mauritius, Rodrigues, and Réunion) represent a crucible of biological evolution. Boasting an astonishing array of biodiversity and a turbulent history of human-induced environmental destruction, the island of Mauritius is an exemplary case study of ecological research, species conservation, and habitat restoration (Cheke and Hume 2008; Florens 2013). Among biologists, Mauritius is best known for its biogeography, species endemism, and as the former home of the dodo (*Raphus cucullatus*), among a host of other extinct and imperiled species (Cheke and Hume 2008). Round Island (19°51'01"S, 57°47'15"E; Fig. 1), located approximately 22 km from the north shore of Mauritius and measuring 219 ha in area, is one of over a dozen islets under the protection and ongoing ecological restoration of the Mauritian government's National Parks and Conservation Service, Mauritian Wildlife Foundation (MWF) and Durrell Wildlife Conservation Trust (Durrell). The poaching of nesting

Fig. 1 Landscapes of Round Island, Mauritius: (a) Basaltic coastal rock carved by wind and rain with neighbouring Gunner’s Quoin (left), Flat (center), and Gabriel islets (right) on horizon; (b) Hurricane Palm (*Dictyosperma album* var. *conjugatum*), the lone *in situ* survivor, stands above a group of endemic Blue Latan Palm (*Latania loddigesii*); (c) rock outcroppings on the northeastern summit; (d) regenerating lowland palm savanna, home to the Round Island stick insect (*Apterograeffea marshallae*). Photos by PD Moldowan

seabirds and now extinct giant tortoises (*Cylindraspis* spp.), introduction of invasive plants, and the release of rabbits (*Oryctolagus cuniculus*) and goats (*Capra hircus*) to the island as food for early mariners resulted in accelerated erosion, extensive destruction of native vegetation, and the loss of native fauna of Round Island (Bullock 1986; Tonge 1989; Tatayah 2010). Today, Round Island is among the few remaining population strongholds, for an unique reptile assemblage consisting of one extant endemic snake (in addition to one snake species now presumed extinct) and six extant endemic lizard species, of which four had become confined to Round Island until recent efforts to reintroduce them back to other islets (Bullock 1986; North et al. 1994; Cole et al. 2009); a native palm community representing the last individuals of their species and varieties (North et al. 1994); and is critical nesting habitat for several seabird species (Tatayah 2010). Temple (1974) emphasized that Round Island “probably has more species of threatened plants and animals per acre than any other piece of land in the world”, earning the island status as a nature reserve in 1957 (Merton 1987). Natural and assisted

recovery of the native vegetation and endemic reptile fauna is beginning to restore the island system towards its pre-anthropogenic state, following the eradication of exotic mammals (North *et al.* 1994; Bullock *et al.* 2002). Attention is now shifting from the recovery of endemic and native plant and vertebrate taxa towards the re-establishment of lost ecological roles. For example, Aldabra Giant Tortoises (*Aldabrachelys gigantea*) and Radiated Tortoises (*Astrochelys radiata*) were introduced to Round Island in 2007 following trials on a smaller Mauritian islet, Île aux Aigrettes (Griffiths *et al.* 2010). These ‘ecological replacements’ are now assisting the management of remaining exotic plants through grazing as well as establishment of native plants through seed dispersal (Griffiths *et al.* 2011, 2013).

In contrast to the extensive effort invested in the recovery of the native plant and vertebrate biota of Mauritius (and elsewhere), the biology and status of native insects remain largely unknown (Motala *et al.* 2007). Over the past decade, entomological research has uncovered a diversity of new species in the Mascarenes with many taxa showing a high degree of endemism and endangerment (eg, Cliquennois and Brock 2004; Hugel 2009, 2010; Hugel *et al.* 2010; Smith and Fisher 2009), and many more likely already extinct. In 2002, a new genus of stick insect (Phasmatodea: Platycraninae: *Apterograeffea*) was described from the Mascarenes with *A. marshallae* described on Round Island (Cliquennois and Brock 2002). Recent molecular research has demonstrated that *A. marshallae* is a member of an ancient lineage originating from Australasia, pre-dating the volcanic origin of Mauritius itself (Bradley *et al.* 2015). The

Fig. 2 Copulating pair of endemic stick insects (Phasmatodea: Platycraninae: *Apterograeffea marshallae*) on the underside of a Blue Latan Palm (*Lantania loddigesii*), Round Island, Mauritius. Photo by PD Moldowan

holotype and paratype of the species were collected on the endemic Blue Latan Palm (*Latania loddigesii*), IUCN Red-Listed as Endangered (IUCN 2016). Cliquennois (2007) suspected the palm to be part of the diet of *A. marshallae* but to date this relationship has not been confirmed. Thus, the objective of this research is to share previously undescribed aspects of *A. marshallae* natural history (diet, reproduction, predation) to inform continued habitat restoration and conservation efforts on Round Island and other islands of the Mascarenes.

Observations

During night surveys between 21:00-00:00 from 08-15th July 2015, pairs of *A. marshallae* were observed mating on the underside of live *L. loddigesii* leaves (Fig 2). Ongoing monitoring by MWF researchers suggests that *A. marshallae* breed year around. In addition, individuals were observed feeding on live leaves of *L. loddigesii*, including a female whilst copulating. In total, 576 *A. marshallae* feeding observations were collected over a 12-month period from July 2006 to June 2007. Feeding observations show that *L. loddigesii* constitutes approximately 90% of the diet of *A. marshallae*, making the palm an important food source. Other food plants included: *Hyophorbe lagenicaulis* (6% of observations), *Elaeodendron (Cassine) orientalis* (2%) and *Dracaena concinna* (2%).

Discussion

Our *A. marshallae* feeding observations confirm dietary speculations by Cliquennois (2007) that the insect feeds on *L. loddigesii* and illustrate an interesting ecological relationship between an endangered plant, a little known insect, and the insular community at large. Among the six lizard species found on Round Island, invertebrates constitute >75% of their diet, by-far the largest contribution of any dietary item (Zuël 2009), suggesting that insects are an integral prey species in this island food web. Furthermore, *A. marshallae* forms approximately 11% of the diet of the endangered Günther's gecko (*Phelsuma guentheri*; N. Zuël unpublished). Large-bodied insects, such as *A. marshallae*, may be especially important links in this insular food web given the extirpation of other invertebrate species, such as the giant tenebrionid beetle (*Polposipus herculeanus*; Cheke and Hume 2008) from Round Island. Also, following extinction of the endemic Mauritian giant tortoises (*Cylindraspis* spp.) and considering the wholly or largely insectivorous diet of all Round Island lizard species, insects such as *A. marshallae* are the only native herbivores that remain on Round Island (notwithstanding the introduction of non-native tortoises as ecological analogues; Griffiths *et al.* 2010).

The only previous record of reproduction in *A. marshallae* reported a mating pair collected in May 2002 (Cliquennois and Brock 2002). Our observations of year around breeding suggest that *A. marshallae* has an extended reproductive period. *Apterograeffea marshallae* is known to glue its eggs to vegetation (Cliquennois and Brock 2002, 2004), however the host plant species is currently unknown. We suggest that in addition to being an important food plant, *L. loddigesii* may be a nursery plant important for reproduction.

As prey, predators, and pollinators, insects can exert top-down and bottom-up trophic interactions, yet insects are disproportionately overlooked as conservation priorities (Motala *et al.* 2007). It is not known if the feeding relationship between *A. marshallae*-*L. loddigesii* is facultative or obligate, the latter of which may be due to food scarcity on Round Island following the destruction of the native plant community. Co-evolved plant-animal interactions, providing ecosystem function, connectivity and services, are particularly vulnerable to extinction in insular ecological communities (Fordham and Brook 2010). The biotic community of Mauritius has experienced the erosion of ecological relationships through the extinction of co-evolved plant-animal species (Griffiths *et al.* 2011). Understanding the biology and conservation of insects is of particular importance in Mauritius, for example, where translocation and habitat restoration projects on surrounding islets (eg, Île aux Aigrettes) are ongoing to establish assurance plant and vertebrate communities that ultimately depend on insect counterparts.

The life history observations of *A. marshallae* may also be relevant to informing the biology of its sister species, *A. reunionensis* on Réunion, and vice versa (Cliquennois and Brock 2002; Bradley *et al.* 2015). Despite search efforts, Cliquennois (2007) was unable to find *A. reunionensis* in association with Réunion's endemic and endangered Red Latan Palm (*Latania lontaroides*; IUCN 2016). However, observations of *A. marshallae* breeding and feeding on Blue Latan Palm on Round Island suggest that continued searching on Réunion's Red Latan Palm is warranted. In captivity, *A. reunionensis* has fed on the rare Hurricane Palm (*Dictyosperma album*; Cliquennois 2007), but on Round Island only one *in situ* wild *D. album* var. *conjugatum* remains (Critically Endangered; IUCN 2016), which may severely limit *A. marshallae*. If the *Dictyosperma* palm is an important dietary item for *Apterograeffea* stick insects, then this palm should be a conservation priority not only for its own persistence but also the support of these endemic stick insects and, perhaps, the ecological interactions of these unique insular communities.

The vegetative community of Round Island has experienced a dramatic change over the past two centuries. In an early description of Round Island, Lloyd (1845) described ravines crowded with *Latania* and areas of the island with a deep, rich soil supporting “the most powerful vegetation” (North and Bullock 1986). By this time, rabbits had already been introduced to the island for at least three decades (ca. 1810) and were reported to be in “immense numbers”, even “swarms” (Lloyd 1845; North and Bullock 1986). Goats were introduced later (ca. 1844-1865) and acted in synergy with the rabbits to cause an extended period of recruitment failure of *Latania*, among many other plant species. Round Island's palm savannah habitat experienced serious destruction and its hardwood forest was extirpated in the century that followed (North and Bullock 1986; Merton 1987). Populations of these introduced mammals persisted unchecked until eradication efforts began for goats (1976-1979) and rabbits (unsuccessfully 1975-1976, completed 1986; Merton 1987; North *et al.* 1994). Even during periods of reduced grazing pressure (1975-1982), between 73-90% of seedlings *Latania* were grazed (North and Bullock 1986). Still, release from grazing pressure between 1975-76 and after 1989 allowed for the first recruitment in decades for many

of the island's plant species (North and Bullock 1986; North et al. 1994). Vegetation surveys between 1975 and 1982 showed that numbers of *Latania* had been greatly reduced through further habitat degradation and the attrition of mature trees from the population, though this palm remained the most abundant tree species on Round Island (North and Bullock 1986). Follow-up surveys in 1989, three years post-eradication of rabbits, documented a marked increase in *Latania* recruitment and reptile population recoveries (Tonge 1989; North et al. 1994) compared to pre-eradication (1975 and 1982; North and Bullock 1986) showing promise for the recovery of Round Island's severely degraded palm savanna. In the years following eradication of introduced mammals the vegetation on Round Island has made a remarkable recovery. In parallel with the recovery of native vegetation, the biomass of invertebrates was predicted to increase post-eradication of mammals (North *et al.* 1994), although this research remains to be seen. While assessments of the biotic community and habitat restoration are ongoing, major hurdles to the re-establishment of native vegetation on Round Island have included: low number of mature trees to provide seed, seed dispersal limitation, competitive displacement from non-native plants, availability of soil (which eroded under intense grazing pressure), water retention of soil, and the burrowing and uprooting of native vegetation by nesting Wedge-Tailed Shearwaters (*Puffinus pacificus*).

Round Island is a stimulating training ground for conservation scientists and is ripe for further research. This short communication represents a call for biodiversity inventories of the Mascarene Islands and conservation awareness for invertebrate taxa. The Mascarene stick insects can serve as large-bodied and charismatic flagship species for conservation, as the wetas (Anostomatidae) have in New Zealand (Watts *et al.* 2008) and giant tenebrionid beetle (*Polposipus herculeanus*) for the Seychelles (Gerlach 2008). Ongoing ecological restoration efforts of the Mascarene Islands and elsewhere would benefit from the directed study of oft-neglected invertebrates to supplement knowledge of species biology and their ecological interactions.

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Corrections and Additons on Lepidoptera from the Seychelles and the Mascarenes

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Abstract: Identifications on two species of lepidoptera from Praslin (Seychelles) are corrected, one species is identified new to Mauritius and two for La Réunion

Key words: Lepidoptera, Seychelles, La Réunion, Mauritius

I was very glad to receive comments and suggestions from Dr.Wolfram Mey and Dr.Klaus Sattler after my earlier publication on Seychelles Lepidoptera (Bippus, 2016). After supplementary studies I would like to communicate some corrections on two of the species illustrated as well as additions on the distribution for two *Mesophleps* species for the Mascarenes.

Gelechiidae:

Mesophleps safranella (Legrand, 1966) – Fig.1-4

Wingspan: 12-14 mm

The identification of the species illustrated on Plate 12, Fig. 53 as *Dichomeris acuminata* (Staudinger, 1876) is wrong and the images show *Mesophleps safranella* (Legrand, 1966).

Supplementary study of specimen collected in La Réunion (Fig. 1-4) showed that this species is also found on this island.

Collection dates from La Réunion, La Possession, alt.400m, 20°55'37''S/55°21'45''E: 10.IX.2015 (female, dissected), 23.IV.2016, 03.V.2016 (male, dissected), 01.VIII.2016, 08.VII.2016, (female, dissected), 10.VIII.2016 (male, dissected), 08/19/21/25/27. IX.2016, 19/26.X.2016, 02.XI.2016.

Mesophleps palpigera (Walsingham, 1891)

Wingspan: 10-11,5 mm

A male specimen collected in Mauritius, Blackriver, alt. 20 m, between 06 to 10.VI.2016 and a female from La Réunion, 18.VIII.2016 proved to be *Mesophleps palpigera*. Both specimens are a little paler and smaller than the collected *Mesophleps safranella* but can easily be confused.

Wingspan: 10mm for the male from Mauritius, 11.5 mm for the female from Réunion.

Plate.1. *Mesophleps safranella* (Legrand, 1966). Fig. 1-2: adult, 13mm. Fig. 3: Male genitalia
Fig. 3b: aedeagus. Fig. 4: Female genitalia

Tineidae:

Tiquadra gypsatma (Meyrick, 1911)

The species illustrated as *Erechthias* sp. nr. *molynta* (Meyrick, 1911) on plate 21, Fig. 89-92 can now be identified as *Tiquadra gypsatma*.

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Notes on Chalcididae (Hymenoptera: Chalcidoidea) from the Seychelles

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Recently the Seychelles species of the superfamily Chalcidoidea have been reviewed by Madl (2013). Seven species of the family Chalcididae are listed from the Inner Seychelles or Seychelles proper. The family is apparently absent from the outer coralline islands (e.g. Aldabra group, Amirantes). The conservation status of the species has been examined by Gerlach (2013). The hosts of the Seychellean species are still unknown.

The paper is based on the material of the Naturhistorisches Museum Wien (Austria). I quite cordially thank Manuela Vizek (Naturhistorisches Museum Wien, Austria) for her support of this study.

Symbols used

§ male

§ female

Faunistics

Subfamily Chalcidinae

Brachymeria lepida (Masi, 1917)

Chalcis lepida n.sp.: Masi 1917: 127 (description § §, Mahé, Anonyme, Silhouette, Denis), 128 (figure 5).

Brachymeria lepida (Masi, 1917): Madl 2006: 1499 (biology, Aride), 1502 (catalogue Aride); Madl 2013: 249 (La Digue, catalogue Seychelles); Gerlach 2013: 367 (red list Seychelles).

Material examined: Mahé: La Gogue Reservoir 1 § 23.5.1996 leg. Madl – Morne Seychellois National Park (Morne Blanc 1 § 27.-28.5.1996 leg. Madl) – Au Cap, La Rousse Hotel 1 § 18.-24.5.1996 leg. Madl – Montagne Brulée 1 § 28.-31.10.1995 leg. Madl – Anse Marie Louise, coconut plantation 1 § 23.5.1996 leg. Madl – Praslin: Nouvelle Decouverte Estate 1 § 29.5.1996 leg. Madl – Anse Boudin 7 §§ 2 §§ 7.-10.6.1999, 17 §§ 31.5.2000 leg. Madl.

Distribution: Inner Seychelles: Mahé, Anonyme, Silhouette, Praslin, La Digue, Aride, Denis.

New to the fauna of Praslin. In the Malagasy subregion *Brachymeria lepida* is also known from Mauritius (Orion 1962 (In: Anonymous): 58). The record from Cameroon (Risbec 1956: 113) should be checked.

***Brachymeria podagrica* (Fabricius, 1787)**

Chalcis amenocles Walker, 1846: Perez 1895: 211 (taxonomy, Mahé).

Chalcis sodalis n.sp.: Masi 1917: 128 (description § \$, Mahé, Silhouette), 129 (figure 6).

Brachymeria podagrica (Fabricius, 1787): Madl 2006: 1499 (biology, Aride), 1502 (catalogue Aride); Madl 2013: 249 (tax., catalogue Seychelles); Gerlach 2013: 367 (red list Seychelles).

Material examined: Mahé: Morne Seychellois National Park (Morne Blanc 1 § 27.-28.5.1996 leg. Madl) – Praslin: Nouvelle Decouverte Estate 1 § 1 § 29. 5. 1996, 1 § 9.6.1999 leg. Madl.

Distribution: Inner Seychelles: Mahé, Silhouette, Praslin, Aride.

New to the fauna of Praslin. *Brachymeria podagrica* is known from all zoogeographical regions. In the Malagasy subregion it has been recorded from Mauritius (Moutia & Mamet 1947: 29 as *Brachymeria neglecta* (Masi, 1916); Orian 1962 (In: Anonymous): 58).

Subfamily Haltichellinae

***Hockeria testaceitarsis* (Cameron, 1907)**

Hockeria testaceitarsis Cameron, 1907: Masi 1917: 130 (tax., description § \$, figures 9.1, 2, Mahé, Anonyme, Silhouette); Madl 2013: 250 (catalogue Seychelles); Gerlach 2013: 367 (red list Seychelles).

Material examined: Mahé: Morne Seychellois National Park (Le Niol, waterworks near Grand Louis River 2 §§ 30. 10. 1991 leg. Madl – Praslin: Anse Boudin 4 §§ 7.-10.6.1999, 2 §§ 31.5.2000 leg. Madl – La Digue: Grande Anse 1 § 1 § 2.6.2000 leg. Madl – Veuve Reserve 3 §§ 2.6.2000 leg. Madl.

Distribution: Inner Seychelles: Mahé, Anonyme, Silhouette, Praslin, La Digue.

New to the fauna of Praslin and La Digue. In the Malagasy subregion *Hockeria testaceitarsis* has been recorded from Mauritius and the Cargados Islands. The record from India (Patel & Patel 1968) should be checked, because *Hockeria testaceitarsis* is not mentioned in Narendran (1986; 1989).

***Notaspidiella frater* (Masi, 1917)**

Hybothorax frater n. sp.: Masi 1917: 134 (description § \$, Mahé, Anonyme), 135 (figure 12).

Notaspidiella frater (Masi, 1917); Madl 2013: 250 (catalogue Seychelles); Gerlach 2013: 367 (red list Seychelles).

Material examined: Mahé: Montagne Posee Road 1 § 3.6.2000 leg. Madl.

Distribution: Inner Seychelles: Mahé, Anonyme.

Notaspidiella frater is endemic to the Inner Seychelles.

Distributional checklist

Antrocephalus mitys (Walker, 1846): Mahé.

Brachymeria lepida (Masi, 1917): Mahé, Anonyme, Silhouette, Praslin, La Digue,

Aride, Denis.

Brachymeria podagrica (Fabricius, 1787): Mahé, Silhouette, Praslin, Aride.

Epitranus clavatus (Fabricius, 1804): Mahé.

Hockeria fulvipes Masi, 1917: Mahé, Silhouette.

Hockeria testaceitarsis Cameron, 1907: Mahé, Anonyme, Silhouette, Praslin, La Digue.

Notaspidiella frater (Masi, 1917): Mahé, Anonyme.

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